

Lean Formalization of Completeness Proofs for Coalition Logic with and without Common Knowledge

K. Obendrauf

Supervisors: Dr. Vera N. Stebletsova and Anne Baanen

Second Reader: Dr. Wan Fokkink

Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, 1081HV Amsterdam, The Netherlands

`k.e.obendrauf@vu.nl`

Abstract. As computers become more commonplace, numerous industries ranging from human-computer interaction to transportation, need to design systems that involve multiple computers and human users. Designing algorithms that meet goals in such multi-agent systems (MAS) is an active research area in Artificial Intelligence. Given the complexity of this problem, modelling is a vital tool to verify design specifications. We build the foundation for such modelling by formalizing a logic that can describe the actions of coalitions of agents: Coalition Logic (CL). An additional challenge in MAS, is that each agent often has access to distinct information. To capture this, we also formalize one extension of CL that can model the individual and common knowledge of agents: Coalition Logic with Common Knowledge (CLC).

We formalize both the syntax and semantics of these logics in the proof assistant Lean. In order to demonstrate that these definitions relate to one another as expected, and can be used in non-trivial proofs, we prove soundness and completeness for both logics. Our implementation emphasises generalizability, by being intentional about constraints in our definitions, leading us to extend CLC to allow common knowledge of the empty set. We also prioritise re-usability by introducing generic Lean classes for types of formulas. These classes can, for instance, prove propositional lemmas for any extension of propositional logic. We hope that these two aspects will make our work extensible for applications in MAS. To this effect, we outline a model-checking algorithm that could check requirements of some MAS design.

Keywords: Multi-agent systems · Coalition Logic · Epistemic Logic · common knowledge · completeness · formal methods · Lean prover

1 Introduction

Computers rarely work in isolation, rather they constantly interact with both human users and other devices. Such interconnected systems can range from household Internet of Things (IoT) devices, working towards creating a useful digital home for a user [2], to critical safety systems in aircraft that communicate their locations and status at all times to nearby peer aircraft [36]. Correctly designing and verifying such systems is an important goal of research in Artificial Intelligence (AI), specifically in the field of Multi Agent Systems (MAS) [5,15,18]. The large number of agents and simultaneous goals involved in these interactions make them highly complex. Furthermore, computers in such systems must often operate with imperfect information [34], for instance because they have limited input about the external environment [15]. It can therefore be difficult to maintain an overview of whether a system has been correctly programmed to always meet its requirements, highlighting the need for formal modelling [18].

1.1 Modelling in Artificial Intelligence

As a simple example of a scenario in MAS that can benefit from such formal modeling, we will compare two (theoretical) designs for a smart light bulb. In our example we have 3 agents: a controller (c) on a smartphone, a receiver (r) on the light bulb which acts on the instructions of the controller, and a physical light switch (p) that can change the state of the light manually. This scenario is modelled in Figure 1.

First imagine that the light is currently off ($\neg l$, where l represents the proposition “the light is on”), and the controller wants to turn it on. The controller can choose to send a signal to the receiver to toggle the state of the light. If no one else acts, this will result in the light turning on. If, however, the physical switch is used before the receiver receives this request, the light switch will turn on momentarily and then be turned back off by the receiver. This means that in order to turn the light on and keep it on, a collaboration is needed between all three agents in our model.

There are several types of logic that are suited to model such a scenario. The turn-based nature of this example could lend itself to a time based logic like Computational Tree Logic (CTL) [33]. For a computer that only receives information periodically, however, breaking those time periods down further into “turns” may not be the most natural implementation. Additionally, this turn based approach does not focus on which groups of agents are required to collaborate in order to meet a requirement. Thus a logic focused on how groups of agents can change the state of the world by their actions is a natural choice; like Coalition Logic (CL) [29] or Alternating Time Temporal Logic (ATL) [3]. The main appeal of CL over other such logics, is that it condenses the actions of multiple agents into a singular accessibility relation. Here, an accessibility relation is a relation over some set of worlds (or states), describing “movement” from one world to another. In ATL, for instance, relations between worlds are

Fig. 1: Smart lightbulb scenario. Components are connected by arrows representing potential information flow. Solid lines reflect physical connections and dashed lines represent wireless connections.

determined based on the starting state and a chosen action for each agent in the model. To know what worlds are accessible from some starting world, we must, therefore, know all possible actions of every agent in the starting state. CL simplifies this information by only storing which coalitions can ensure which sets of outcomes. More specifically, given some starting state and coalition this accessibility relation, called an effectivity structure, outputs all sets of worlds, such that the coalition can ensure ending up in some world in the set.

We can use this effectivity structure to model one possible design for the smart light bulb. This design is illustrated by the solid lines in Figure 2a. In our example, a coalition between all three agents ($\{c, r, p\}$) from W_1 can ensure the light turns on (W_3). In the diagram, the line connecting W_1 to W_3 is thus labelled with all three agents. The controller and receiver on their own however can only ensure that the light turns either on or off (W_3 or W_4), but cannot specify which, as the physical switch can always be used to “undo” the controllers instruction. In Figure 2a, this is implied by the fact that the only arrows from W_1 go to W_3 and W_4 , but both arrows are labelled by the coalition $\{c, r, p\}$. The arrows are labelled by the minimal coalition(s) required to ensure this transition. Thus, if the controller and receiver were sufficient to ensure travelling specifically to W_3 , that arrow would be labelled $\{c, r\}$. We also add relations from W_3 and W_4 , for the next time the lightbulb is used. In Figure 2a, this looks like the receiver immediately updating the controller on the current state, ready for the controller to decide on the next instruction.

We can compare this design to one where the controller and receiver on their own are enough to ensure the outcome state of the lightbulb. In this case, rather

Fig. 2: Comparison of two lightbulb designs, modelled with CL with knowledge operators. Solid arrows refer to all possible transitions between states. They are labelled with the smallest possible coalition(s) that can ensure the transition happens. All other effectivity structure outcomes can be assumed. The dotted lines in both figures represent knowledge relations labelled by the agent they apply to. Reflexive knowledge arrows are implied. These graphs are described more formally in Sections 2.3 & 3.2.

than the controller sending a single instruction based on the initial state of the light bulb, the controller might send all possible instructions. For instance, the controller may send the instruction: if the light is off turn it on, otherwise do nothing. This allows the receiver to check its own state effectively at the same time as it acts, regardless of whether the physical switch was used while the controller was deciding on and sending this instruction. The design is modeled by the solid lines in Figure 2b. We again add relations from W_3 and W_4 to this design. These model the time it may take the controller to decide its new instructions during which time the physical switch may be used. Note that in this design there are many implied outcomes. For instance, from W_1 the coalition $\{c, r, p\}$ can ensure W_3 because $\{c, r\}$ can ensure it. Similarly, from W_1 $\{c, r\}$ can ensure W_3 or W_1 by ensuring W_3 .

From these descriptions, it may seem like we should decide whether we want the controller and receiver to be able to ensure their outcome, and pick our design accordingly. This, however, paints an incomplete picture. In the first design we begin with knowledge about the state of the light bulb. In the second design this knowledge is not required and therefore missing. The controller and receiver can therefore ensure the state of the light bulb, at the cost of the controller knowing if the light bulb was ever in an undesired starting state. The first design forfeits control over the outcome to give the controller more information about the starting state of the system, and thus which action the receiver performs (toggle the light or not). We can add this aspect to our models by adding knowledge (epistemic) relations. This means we are now modelling our designs with CL with Knowledge operators [1]. For each agent we add a knowledge relation, connecting the worlds they cannot tell apart. These are indicated by the dotted

lines in the Figures (reflexive arrows implied): in Figure 2a the controller does not know the result of its action, and in Figure 2b the controller does not know the state of the light bulb before acting.

The smart light bulb may seem like a trivial example, but the difference between these two designs parallels the difference between Imperative and Declarative management when managing computers. In imperative management commands are sent to a device assuming we have correct knowledge about its current state [19]. Declarative management, meanwhile, informs a device how to reach a goal state given that it first assesses its current state [20]. This example thus encapsulates real differences in how organisations implement security requirements on their devices. Modelling these systems may then help clarify which system is better for one specific organizations goals. In this way modal logic can thus be used as a powerful tool for reasoning about and even designing solutions in MAS [18].

Several other real-world systems already use modal logic to check requirements and ensure safety, including checking safety-critical properties of a driverless metro in Paris [21] and verifying that traffic light control systems are working correctly [37]. It is not difficult to think about such examples in terms of multiple agents (multiple trains or cars) and the potential for incomplete knowledge (for instance failing sensors or unpredictable human agents). CL with knowledge operators is thus a naturally useful modal logic to investigate further and potentially implement in real world systems.

1.2 Goal of this work: Modelling Coalition Logic with Knowledge Operators in a Proof Assistant

Given the potential benefits of modelling MAS designs, it becomes beneficial to create computer-readable versions of these models. Furthermore, for real-life use cases these models would quickly grow incredibly large, given multiple agents and possible states [18]. It is not hard to imagine losing overview of such a model, and for potential mistakes to slip in. It would, therefore, be incredibly helpful to programmatically verify that it has been modelled correctly, and that the design (and thus the model) meets its requirements. In this instance, we need to describe models and proofs in CL with knowledge operators programmatically.

The natural tools for building and checking logical models and statements are proof assistants, as they are specifically designed to verify logical proofs. The current research thus aims to build a foundation for such applications by investigating how CL with knowledge operators can be defined, and reasoned with in a proof assistant. More specifically we will look at formalizing CL with Common Knowledge (CLC) [1]. We describe this logic in more detail in Section 3.

When modelling knowledge relations 3 epistemic operators are commonly used: individual knowledge, common knowledge and distributed knowledge. We choose to investigate CLC, thus implementing only the first two operators. This choice limits the scale of the current work, while still allowing for additional complexity from the two new operators.

The first step towards formalizing CLC would require defining the syntax and semantics of this logic with a proof assistant. This can already present challenges, as one has to formalize details about implementation that can simply be assumed in paper proofs due to convention, or their trivial nature [13]. For this reason we also formalize soundness and completeness of the defined logic, to support that it was implemented correctly. Furthermore, doing so acts as an example about how one can reason with the defined logic in a proof assistant to prove non trivial theorems. Given this goal, we will now take a closer look at proof assistants and their capabilities.

1.3 Proof Assistants and Lean

Proof assistants are a set of software tools that allow users to build and check proofs in a logical calculus [4,13]. Moreover, proof assistants can be very helpful in exploring how a proof can be generalized, or modified. For instance, one can relatively quickly see instances of unused assumptions. This provides an additional advantage to formalizing logical proofs with a proof assistant [4].

Of the many different proof assistants, including Isabelle/HOL [27], Agda [8], and Coq [28], Lean was chosen for the current research. The choice was made due to Lean’s large existing repertoire of important data-structures, existing theorems, and proofs in the open source Lean library *mathlib* [31], which are relevant for the proofs of the current research [26]. Lean is a relatively new proof assistant, first developed at Microsoft Research by Leonardo de Moura in 2013 [24]. It checks proofs in the dependently typed Calculus of Inductive Constructions [7,10,26].

1.4 Related work

The formalization of modal logics in proof assistants is an active area of research. To our knowledge CLC has not yet been formalized in any proof assistant, however our work builds on related work on formalizing Epistemic Logics (EL) and CL. We start by describing work in CL. Nalon *et al.* [25] present a prototype automated reasoning tool for CL, based on a sound, complete, and terminating resolution-based calculus for CL, in SWI-Prolog. On the other hand, Baston and Capretta [6], focused more on proving the fundamental theorems of CL than reasoning with it. They propose to use Coq to formalize a proof about how effectivity structures, given a specific starting state, relate to strategic games. These works provide support that CL can be defined and reasoned with in proof assistants. However, to the best of our knowledge, at this point in time there are no current works that formalize completeness of CL by canonical model constructions in any proof assistant, nor has any project formalized CL in the proof assistant Lean.

In contrast there are several existing formalizations of EL both in Lean [7,23,26] and other proof assistants [9,11,22]. In Lean, the first of these was the completeness proof of EL (S5) by Bentzen [7]. Following this, both Neeley [26] and Li [23], formalized completeness again, but with different approaches,

showing how flexibly such proofs can be implemented in Lean. Additionally both these works also built on their proof for EL to show completeness of Public Announcement Logic (PA) [23,26]. This addition is particularly interesting to us as it shows that formalizations of different logics can be built onto each other in Lean. This “buildability” should allow researchers to build off each others work, allowing for more collaboration and quicker progress. Thus the current research aims to, as much as possible, build off of existing implementations in Lean when working on our own goals. Furthermore, we aim to research how to write our own formalizations and proofs in such a way that they are as generalizable and reusable as possible, also for other types of logic.

1.5 Research Questions and Approach

As previously mentioned, the main goal of the current research is to investigate formalizing and reasoning about CL with knowledge operators in Lean, by proving soundness and completeness of CLC. This section outlines our approach to exploring this goal, guided by the following three research questions:

RQ1: *How do soundness and completeness proofs of CLC work in Lean?*

Investigating soundness and completeness proofs of CLC in Lean allows us to check that the syntax and semantics of CLC defined in Lean relate to one another as expected. Additionally, doing so demonstrates that these definitions can be used in non trivial proofs about CLC. Ågotnes and Alechina [1] provide a paper proof of the soundness and completeness of CLC. In the current work, we thus aim to formalize these proofs in the proof assistant Lean. We will follow the paper proof as closely as possible, defining first the syntax, semantics and axioms of CLC, and then prove soundness and completeness. Formalizing with a proof assistant, however, often requires quite a lot of additional details, for example specifying trivial assumptions. Thus, we will first elaborate on the paper proof and specify missing trivial or common-sense steps. Adding these details allows the Lean proof to match the paper proof much more closely.

Once we have a more thorough written proof, we will begin translating it into Lean. Although we aim to make the written proof translate as directly as possible into Lean, we will also take advantage of the proof assistant’s ability to test for generalizability. In practice, this will mean looking for unused assumptions and being as specific as possible about when assumptions are needed, and when they are not. Another way the Lean proof will differ from even a more detailed paper proof, is that in Lean many additional implementation choices will be needed. For example we will need to pick which Lean data structures to use for different definitions. We will, therefore, defer to existing work [7,23,26] on formalizing EL in Lean for guidance on implementation choices. Most often, we will look to the project by Neeley [26], as this proof style matches the type of proof by Ågotnes and Alechina [1] quite closely, while being particularly detailed about their design decisions. Furthermore, likely due to the large number of logics formalized by Neeley

(K, T, S4, S5 and PA) [26], their design decisions are relatively easy to generalize to other types of logic.

Importantly, the paper proof for completeness of CLC [1] builds on Pauly’s original proof of completeness for CL [29]. Thus, in order to follow the proof for CLC, we will first need to build the canonical model used for proving completeness of CL. Given this, we define the two remaining research questions:

RQ2: *How do soundness and completeness proofs of CL work in Lean?*

Given that we need to follow the structure of Pauly’s completeness proof for CL [29] to prove completeness of CLC [1], we choose to simply start by defining and proving soundness and completeness for CL in Lean. Doing so provides an additional example of the capabilities and potential advantages of using Lean for soundness and completeness proofs. Our approach is the same as for CLC, except this time we follow the paper proof by Pauly [29] as closely as possible.

RQ3: *How can definitions of and theorems about CL in Lean be reused for CLC?*

Exploring soundness and completeness proofs for both CL and CLC provides the perfect opportunity to explore the potential for modularity in such Lean proofs. Especially since CLC builds on CL, it would be useful to reuse as many definitions and theorems as possible. Thus, this research aims to investigate how to extend CL into CLC in the most natural and replicable way possible. We aim to devise data structures and a methodology for intuitively adding knowledge operators, so that in the future other operators can be added with ease.

All of the code for this project can be found at <https://github.com/kaioendrauf/cl-lean>.

2 Formalizing Coalition Logic in Lean

CL is a type of modal logic introduced by Pauly [29] to reason about how groups of agents can change the state of the world by their actions. More specifically, given a finite non-empty set of agents N , a non-empty set of states S , and a set of propositions Φ_0 , CL allows us to reason about the ability of some group $G \subseteq N$ to ensure we end up in a state where some property holds. For instance, in our light bulb example in Figure 2b, the coalition $\{c, r\}$ can ensure from W_1 that the light will be on (represented by the proposition l) by ensuring we move to W_3 . This ability to ensure an outcome is captured in CL by the accessibility relation, which condenses the actions of multiple agents into a singular relation. Thus, CL uses the standard propositional operators plus the effectivity operator, where $[G]\varphi$ means that the group of agents $G \subseteq N$ is effective for ensuring φ , regardless of the actions of other agents. These effectivity structures need to accurately describe all possible consequences of all possible coalitions from each starting world. We will explore effectivity structures in depth in Section 2.1, describing the formal requirements of effectivity structures and how to translate

these to Lean. Following this we will formalize the syntax, semantics, and axioms of CL in Lean in Sections 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 respectively. Lastly, we will use these definitions to prove completeness of CL in Lean in Section 2.5.

2.1 Effectivity and Playability

As already mentioned the hallmark characteristic of CL is the effectivity operator: $[G]\varphi$. If some group G is effective for ensuring some outcome φ this means that there must **exist** a strategy for G such that **for all** strategies of the agents not in G we ensure we end up in some state where φ holds. This type of $\exists - \forall$ ability is called α -ability. Here, as in standard semantics of modal logic, we are interpreting formulas with respect to a given state, and the outcome of all agents' actions results in moving between states. It is important to note that a coalition does not have to ensure ending up in one specific world in order to ensure some outcome. Rather it may restrict the set of states it is possible to move such that the desired outcome holds in all of those possible states. In CL, the function that maps what some group of agents are effective in achieving from some starting state is called an *effectivity structure*.

Definition 1 (Effectivity Structure). *Given a non-empty set of states S , and a non-empty, finite set of agents N , an effectivity structure maps a state and subset of N to a set of subsets of S , which we write as taking the form $E : S \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(N) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{P}(S))$.*

Given some state $s \in S$ and set of agents $G \subseteq N$, $E(s)(G)$ results in a set of sets of states. From s , for any set $X \in E(s)(G)$, the coalition G can ensure we will end up in some state $t \in X$. This function can be intuitively defined in Lean as having the type:

```
1 def effectivity_struct (agents states : Type) :=
2   states → (set agents) → (set (set (states)))
```

The first line of the definition can be read intuitively as: an effectivity structure is defined over some set of agents (in the paper proof this is N), and some set of states (in the paper proof this is S). The rest of the definition describes the function form. We have two inputs, first `states` which refers to some element which is a state (in Lean terms these elements are of the `Type` `states`). The second input to the function is `set agents` which refers to some set that contains only elements which are agents, and thus must be an element of $\mathcal{P}(N)$. After the last arrow we see the Lean `Type` of the output of the function; a set of sets of states.

In order to use this function to model α -effectivity however, it must satisfy certain properties. An effectivity structure which satisfies these requirements is called a *playable* effectivity structure.

Playability. There are five conditions of playability. We define each condition first in words and then as a logical formula, to begin the process of formalization. Following this we will translate the conditions into Lean definitions.

Definition 2 (Playable Effectivity Structure). *An effectivity structure E is playable iff, for each state s , the following five conditions are met:*

1. $E(s)$ is live, meaning groups can never ensure being in no state, and thus can never ensure a contradiction.
 $\forall G \subseteq N : \emptyset \notin E(s)(G)$
2. $E(s)$ is safe, meaning all groups can be indifferent about the outcome.
 $\forall G \subseteq N : S \in E(s)(G)$
3. $E(s)$ is N -maximal, meaning that if $X^c = S \setminus X$ is not guaranteed then all agents together must be effective in achieving X , where X^c is the compliment of X .
 $\forall X \subseteq S : X^c \notin E(s)(\emptyset) \Rightarrow X \in E(s)(N)$
4. $E(s)$ is outcome monotonic, meaning that if a group can ensure X , it can ensure any set of outcomes that includes (all of) X .
 $\forall C \subseteq N, \forall X \subseteq Y \subseteq S : X \in E(s)(G) \Rightarrow Y \in E(s)(G)$
5. $E(s)$ is superadditive, meaning that if two mutually exclusive groups can ensure X and Y respectively, then working together they can ensure both.
 $\forall C, D \subseteq N$ (where $C \cap D = \emptyset$) , $\forall X, Y \subseteq S : X \in E(s)(G)$ and $Y \in E(s)(D) \Rightarrow X \cap Y \in E(s)(C \cup D)$

In Lean, we can translate a mathematical object that satisfies some requirements into a tuple. One of the elements of the tuple (often the first element) contains the mathematical object itself, and then each remaining element of the tuple contains a proof that one of the requirements is met. Thus, to represent a playable effectivity structure, we create a 6-tuple to link the effectivity function itself to the 5 playability requirements. The type of all tuples of a certain shape can be defined as a Lean **structure** data-type. More formally, a Lean **structure** is a non-recursive, single-constructor, inductive type [4], which allows one to create a tuple of different kinds of information. We can therefore, define `playable_effectivity_struct` as a Lean **structure** to take the shape of a tuple containing an effectivity structure `E` and, for each of the 5 playability requirements, a proof that `E` meets this requirement.

First N -maximality, which will be needed outside of the scope of playability later on, is defined as follows:

```

1 def N_max {agents states : Type}
2   (E : (effectivity_struct agents states)) :=
3    $\forall s : \text{states}, \forall X : \text{set states},$ 
4    $(X^c \notin E (s) (\emptyset)) \rightarrow (X \in E (s) (\text{univ}))$ 

```

The first two lines of the definition can be read intuitively as: N -maximality is defined over some set of agents, some set of states, and some effectivity structure (E). The rest of the definition directly corresponds to the N -maximality condition. Note that in Lean we use `univ` to refer to the universal set (in this case N). We need to do this because Lean is based on type theory, so it distinguishes `agents : Type` from the universal set N .

It is the reference to the universal set that makes this definition particularly important, as it describes special cases of the effectivity structure: when the

coalition is empty and when it is full. These cases, especially the latter, are often treated separately in the upcoming proofs. Informally $E(s)(\emptyset)$ can be seen to describe the movements that cannot be avoided, as for all $X \in E(s)(\emptyset)$ we have to end up in some state $t \in X$, regardless of the actions of any agent. $E(s)(N)$ on the other hand, can be seen to describe all the possible movements, as when all agents work together, any possible strategy combinations and resulting outcome can be ensured.

Once we have defined N-maximality, the playable effectivity structure is defined as follows:

```

1 structure playable_effectivity_struct (agents states : Type) :=
2   (E           : effectivity_struct agents states)
3   (liveness    :  $\forall s : \text{states}, \forall G : \text{set agents}, \emptyset \notin E(s)(G)$ )
4   (safety      :  $\forall s : \text{states}, \forall G : \text{set agents}, \text{univ} \in E(s)(G)$ )
5   (N_max       : N_max E)
6   (mono        :  $\forall s : \text{states}, \forall G : \text{set agents}, \forall X Y : \text{set states},$ 
7                  $X \subseteq Y \rightarrow X \in E(s)(G) \rightarrow Y \in E(s)(G)$ )
8   (superadd    :  $\forall s : \text{states}, \forall G F : \text{set agents},$ 
9                  $\forall X Y : \text{set states},$ 
10                   $X \in E(s)(G) \rightarrow Y \in E(s)(F) \rightarrow G \cap F = \emptyset \rightarrow$ 
11                   $X \cap Y \in E(s)(G \cup F)$ )

```

The first line can be read as: given some agents and some states, we can define playable effectivity structure as a Lean **structure** over those agents and states. The rest of the Lean **structure** declaration defines the form which elements of `playable_effectivity_struct` should take, namely a 6-tuple where each field has the specified Lean **Type**. The playability conditions are included as proof terms in the Lean **structure**. This means that when instantiating a `playable_effectivity_struct` one must provide proofs that these conditions are met. Each part of the tuple can be accessed with dot notation: `play.liveness` would access the proof that the effectivity structure `play.E` is live.

Semi-playability. Related to playability we have the notion of semi-playability, which omits N-maximality and specifies that the playability conditions only need to be met for groups G that are a strict subset of N ($G \subset N$).

Definition 3 (Semi-Playability). *An effectivity structure E is semi-playable iff, for any state s :*

1. $E(s)$ is live for all $G \subset N$.
 $\forall G \subset N : \emptyset \notin E(s)(G)$
2. $E(s)$ is safe for all $G \subset N$.
 $\forall G \subset N : S \in E(s)(G)$
3. $E(s)$ is outcome-monotonic for all $G \subset N$.
 $\forall G \subset N, \forall X \subseteq Y \subseteq S : X \in E(s)(G) \Rightarrow Y \in E(s)(G)$

4. $E(s)$ is superadditive for all $G \cup F \subset N$.
 $\forall G, F \subseteq N$ (where $G \cap F = \emptyset$ and $G \cup F \subset N$), $\forall X, Y \subseteq S : X \in E(s)(G)$
and $Y \in E(s)(F) \Rightarrow X \cap Y \in E(s)(G \cup F)$

A semi-playable effectivity structure is defined in Lean analogously to a playable one.

```

1 structure semi_playable_effectivity_struct
2   (agents states : Type) :=
3   (E           : effectivity_struct agents states)
4   (semi_liveness :  $\forall s : \text{states}, \forall G : \text{set agents},$ 
5                    $G \subset \text{univ} \rightarrow \emptyset \notin E (s) (G)$ )
6   (semi_safety  :  $\forall s : \text{states}, \forall G : \text{set agents},$ 
7                    $G \subset \text{univ} \rightarrow \text{univ} \in E (s) (G)$ )
8   (semi_mono    :  $\forall s : \text{states}, \forall G : \text{set agents},$ 
9                    $\forall X Y : \text{set states}, G \subset \text{univ} \rightarrow$ 
10                   $X \subseteq Y \rightarrow X \in E (s) (G) \rightarrow Y \in E (s) (G)$ )
11  (semi_superadd :  $\forall s : \text{states}, \forall G F : \text{set agents},$ 
12                   $\forall X Y : \text{set states}, G \cup F \subset \text{univ} \rightarrow$ 
13                   $X \in E (s) (G) \rightarrow Y \in E (s) (F) \rightarrow$ 
14                   $G \cap F = \emptyset \rightarrow X \cap Y \in E (s) (G \cup F)$ )

```

Playability from Semi-playability. The notion of semi-playability is helpful as, along with N-maximality and regularity, semi-playability is sufficient for playability.

Definition 4 (Regularity). *An effectivity structure E is regular iff, for any state s , when some group can ensure X , the remaining agents cannot ensure that we avoid X .*

$$\forall s \in S, \forall G \subseteq N, \forall X \subseteq S : X \in E(s)(G) \Rightarrow X^c \notin E(s)(G^c)$$

Informally, regularity says that if some group can ensure X , the agents not in the group cannot ensure that we avoid X . In Lean we can define this as follows:

```

1 def regular {agents states : Type}
2   (E : (effectivity_struct agents states)) :=
3    $\forall s : \text{states}, \forall G : \text{set agents}, \forall X : \text{set states},$ 
4    $(X \in E (s) (G)) \rightarrow (X^c \notin E (s) (G^c))$ 

```

Being able to define playability from semi-playability, N-maximality and regularity vastly simplifies proving playability in cases when the definition of E distinguishes between the cases $G = N$ and $G \subset N$. In Lean we thus can set up a function that constructs a playable effectivity structure given a semi-playable effectivity structure and a proof of N-maximality and regularity.

```

1 def playable_from_semi_Nmax_reg {agents : Type} (states : Type)
2   [ha : nonempty agents]
3   (semi : semi_playable_effectivity_struct agents states)
4   (hNmax : N_max semi.E) (hReg : regular semi.E) :
5   playable_effectivity_struct agents states := ...

```

The proof itself will be described below in Lemma 1.

Note that this definition is the first time that we require N , or in this case our agents : **Type** , to be nonempty (in line 2). We have chosen to only formalize requirements about our agents when they are directly required by the proofs. Doing so keeps our definitions as general as possible, but it is of course easy to add additional requirements when needed. In this case, we did not need to specify that N was non-empty when defining a (semi-) playable effectivity structure. The ability to define playability from semi-playability, does however rely on the fact that N is non-empty, so we have introduced this requirement now. Introducing these hypotheses only when explicitly needed both simplifies definitions and keeps track of what these additional hypotheses are achieving.

Lemma 1 ([29, Lemma 3.4]). *Proving that an effectivity structure E is semi-playable, regular and N -maximal, suffices to prove that E is playable.*

The detailed proof for this is expanded from Pauly [29]. Most importantly we explicitly add to Pauly’s proof all the trivial and analogous steps. Additionally, we are explicit about all assumptions and conclusions, as this allows us to translate these more directly to Lean. As an example of this translation to Lean, we have included the portion of the Lean proof showing liveness. The remainder of this proof is translated to Lean with a similar level of directness.

Proof. For the playability requirements liveness, safety, and outcome monotonicity proofs follow fairly directly from their matching semi-playable condition with regularity or N -maximality. For superadditivity the proof follows from the fact that at least one set of agents G or F , must be a subset of N .

1. Let E be a semi-playable, regular, N -maximal effectivity structure. Let $s \in S$ be any state.

2. $E(s)$ is live: $\emptyset \notin E(s)(N)$.

From semi-playable safety: $S \in E(s)(\emptyset)$ and regularity: $S \in E(s)(\emptyset) \Rightarrow \emptyset \notin E(s)(N)$. This is translated to Lean as follows:

```

1 have hS : univ ∈ semi.E (s) (∅),
2   from semi.semi_safety s ∅ (empty_subset_univ ha),
3 have hif : univ ∈ semi.E (s) (∅) → univc ∉ semi.E (s) (∅c),
4   from hReg s ∅ univ,
5 simp[compl_univ, compl_empty] at hif,
6 exact hif hS,

```

Here line 1 states that $S \in E(s)(\emptyset)$ holds, and line 2 proves this fact from semi-playable safety. Similarly lines 3-4 correspond to our statement about regularity, however note here that we have to use univ^c for \emptyset , and \emptyset^c for N . Thus we need to explicitly convince Lean that these pairs of sets are equivalent, which we do in line 6 using existing lemmas from Lean’s *mathlib* library. Lastly we can combine the two statements to reach our final conclusion in line 6.

3. $E(s)$ is safe: $S \in E(s)(N)$.

From semi-playable liveness: $\emptyset \notin E(s)(\emptyset)$ and N -maximality: $\emptyset \notin E(s)(\emptyset) \Rightarrow S \in E(s)(N)$.

4. $E(s)$ is outcome monotonic: $\forall X \subseteq Y \subseteq S : X \in E(s)(N) \Rightarrow Y \in E(s)(N)$.
 - 4.1. Let X and Y be some sets such that $X \subseteq Y \subseteq S$ and $X \in E(s)(N)$.
 - 4.2. $X^c \notin E(s)(\emptyset)$, from regularity: $X \in E(s)(N) \Rightarrow X^c \notin E(s)(\emptyset)$, and 4.1.
 - 4.3. $Y^c \subseteq X^c$, because $X \subseteq Y$ (from 4.1).
 - 4.4. $Y^c \in E(s)(\emptyset) \Rightarrow X^c \in E(s)(\emptyset)$, from semi-playable outcome monotonicity and 4.3.
 - 4.5. $X^c \notin E(s)(\emptyset) \Rightarrow Y^c \notin E(s)(\emptyset)$, from the contrapositive of 4.4.
 - 4.6. $Y^c \notin E(s)(\emptyset)$, from 4.2 and 4.5.
 - 4.7. $Y \in E(s)(N)$, from N-maximality: $Y^c \notin E(s)(\emptyset) \Rightarrow Y \in E(s)(N)$ and 4.6.
5. $E(s)$ is superadditive: $\forall G, F \subseteq N$ (where $G \cap F = \emptyset$ and $G \cup F = N$), $\forall X, Y \subseteq S : X \in E(s)(G)$ and $Y \in E(s)(F) \Rightarrow X \cap Y \in E(s)(G \cup F)$.
 - 5.1. Let $G, F \subseteq N$, be some sets where $G \cap F = \emptyset$ and $G \cup F = N$. Note that $G = F^c$.
 - 5.2. Either $F \subset N$ or $G \subset N$ (or both), from 5. Let F' be either F or G , such that $F' \subset N$, and let G' be the other set.
 - 5.3. Let X, Y be any sets such that $X \in E(s)(G')$ and $Y \in E(s)(F')$.
 - 5.4. Assume towards a contradiction that $X \cap Y \notin E(s)(G' \cup F')$. Note that $G' \cup F' = N$.
 - 5.5. $(X \cap Y) \notin E(s)(N) \Rightarrow (X \cap Y)^c \in E(s)(\emptyset)$, from the contrapositive of N-maximality: $(X \cap Y)^c \notin E(s)(\emptyset) \Rightarrow (X \cap Y) \in E(s)(N)$.
 - 5.6. $(X \cap Y)^c \in E(s)(\emptyset)$, from 5.4 and 5.5.
 - 5.7. $((X \cap Y)^c \cap Y) \in E(s)(F')$, from semi-playability superadditivity: $(X \cap Y)^c \in E(s)(\emptyset)$ and $Y \in E(s)(F') \Rightarrow ((X \cap Y)^c \cap Y) \in E(s)(\emptyset \cup F')$, and from 5.3 and 5.6.
 - 5.8. $(X^c \cap Y) \in E(s)(F')$, from 5.7.
 - 5.9. $X^c \in E(s)(F')$, from semi-playability outcome monotonicity: $(X^c \cap Y) \in E(s)(F') \Rightarrow X^c \in E(s)(F')$, and 5.8.
 - 5.10. $X \notin E(s)(G')$, from regularity: $X^c \in E(s)(F') \Rightarrow X \notin E(s)(G')$, and 5.9, given $(F')^c = G'$, from 5.1.
 - 5.11. Contradiction from 5.10 and 5.3.
6. From 2, 3, 4, 5 and N-maximality, we have playability.

2.2 Syntax

Recall that given a finite, non-empty set of agents N , and a set of atomic propositions Φ_0 , a CL formula is constructed from the usual propositional logic operators and the effectivity operator $[G]\varphi$, where $G \subseteq N$ is a set of agents. This operator can intuitively be read as “coalition group G is effective in bringing about φ , regardless of the actions of agents not in the coalition”. In other words, the coalition has the α -ability to bring about φ . CL is defined by the following BNF grammar:

$$\varphi := \perp \mid p \mid \varphi \wedge \varphi \mid \varphi \rightarrow \varphi \mid [G]\varphi$$

where $p \in \Phi_0$ and $G \subseteq N$. For readability, when using the effectivity operator for singleton sets we write $[i]\varphi$ instead of $\{\{i\}\}\varphi$.

In order to prove metatheoretical results about CL, such as soundness and completeness, the logic is encoded using a deep embedding [17,26]. This deep embedding means that both the syntax and semantics of the language are explicitly defined, rather than representing them with equivalent logic already defined in Lean [17,26]. By explicitly defining the syntax and semantics in this way we can much more easily write inductive proofs on them, which are needed for metatheoretical results. Thus, in Lean, the language of CL formulas is defined as an inductive Lean **Type**, meaning the smallest type closed under the operators `bot`, `var`, `and`, `imp`, and `eff`, as shown below:

```

1 inductive formCL (agents : Type) : Type
2   | bot                                     : formCL
3   | var (n : nat)                          : formCL
4   | and (ϕ ψ : formCL)                     : formCL
5   | imp (ϕ ψ : formCL)                    : formCL
6   | eff (G : set agents) (ϕ : formCL)     : formCL

```

Two types of atomic formulas are defined: \perp , and the propositional variables $p \in \Phi_0$. In Lean we chose to index the atomic variables by the natural numbers, as in the work by Neeley [26]. Based on the finding by Neeley that using a non-minimal set of propositional connectives simplifies some inductive proofs, both the `imp`, and `and` operators are included. The final `eff` operator represents the effectivity operator.

For readability, shorthand notation is introduced for CL operators so that Lean's notation matches paper notation more closely. The remaining propositional operators (\top , \vee , and \leftrightarrow) are defined as usual.

```

1 notation `!⊥`      : 80 := formCL.bot
2 infix    `!∧`     : 79 := formCL.and
3 infixr   `!→`     : 78 := formCL.imp
4 notation `!¬`     : 80 ϕ := ϕ '→' '!⊥
5 notation `![ G `]` : 80 ϕ := formCL.eff G ϕ
6 notation `!⊤`     : 80 := '!¬ ('!⊥)
7 notation ϕ `!∨` ψ : 79 := '!¬ ((!¬ ϕ) '∧' (!¬ ψ))
8 notation ϕ `!↔` ψ : 78 := (ϕ '→' ψ) '∧' (ψ '→' ϕ)

```

2.3 Semantics

Frames and models in CL are defined with a playable effectivity structure as the accessibility structure.

Definition 5 (Coalition Frame). *A coalition frame is a tuple $F = (S, E)$, where:*

*S is a non-empty set of states
 $E : S \rightarrow (\mathcal{P}(N) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{P}(S)))$ is a playable effectivity structure*

A CL frame is a tuple, so in Lean we define it as a Lean `structure`. Thus, we define a frame as follows:

```

1 structure frameCL (agents : Type) :=
2   (states : Type)
3   (hs      : nonempty states)
4   (E      : playable_effectivity_struct agents states)

```

Here we add the requirement for S to be nonempty as a proof term in the Lean `structure`. We note here that this requirement is never explicitly used and thus we could generalize our definition by removing it, in the same way that we exclude the requirements for N to be non-empty and finite. We choose to include this requirement about S , however, because we will later build S as a set of sets of formulas. This requirement, thus, acts as a check that S has been defined correctly. For this reason we would likely choose to prove that S is non-empty even if it was not required by our `structure` `frameCL` definition. Given this, we simply choose to include this requirement directly in the `structure` `frameCL` definition. It would not, however, be difficult to remove, and the rest of the proof would function the same regardless.

Given a coalition frame, we define a coalition model as usual, by adding a valuation function to a coalition frame.

Definition 6 (Coalition Model). *A coalition model is a tuple $M = (F, V)$, where:*

F : is a coalition frame
 $V : \Phi_0 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(S)$ is the usual valuation function, assigning a set $V(s) \subseteq \Phi_0$ to each state $s \in S$

In Lean, a coalition model is again defined as a Lean `structure`.

```

1 structure modelCL (agents : Type) :=
2   (f : frameCL agents)
3   (v : N → set f.states)

```

Here, in line 3, the valuation function has the form $\mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(S)$ because propositional variables are indexed by natural numbers.

Formally Describing Two Example Coalition Models. Given this formal definition of a coalition model, we now provide formal descriptions of our example models in Figure 2, excluding the knowledge relations (represented by dotted lines).

Call the model in Figure 2a: $M^a = (F^a, V^a)$, where $F^a = (S^a, E^a)$ and the model in Figure 2b: $M^b = (F^b, V^b)$, where $F^b = (S^b, E^b)$. For both models, $N = \{c, r, p\}$ and $\Phi_0 = \{l\}$. Both models also have their states and valuation functions in common: $S^a = S^b = \{W_1, W_2, W_3, W_4\}$, and $V^a(l) = V^b(l) = \{W_1, W_3\}$. Thus both models only differ in their effectivity structures. Many of the inputs for effectivity structure lead to the same output, therefore for readability we will

combine these, giving instead two sets as input such that for any input from the first set and any input from the second set, the effectivity structures will result in the same output. For example, $E^a\{W_1, W_2\}\{\{c\}, \{r\}\} = X$, represents $E^a(W_1)(\{c\}) = E^a(W_2)(\{c\}) = E^a(W_1)(\{r\}) = E^a(W_2)(\{r\}) = X$. This allows us to define E^a and E^b as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E^a\{W_1, W_2\} \{G \mid G \subset N\} &= \{X \mid \{W_3, W_4\} \subseteq X\} \\
 E^a\{W_1, W_2\} \{N\} &= \{X \mid \{W_3\} \subseteq X\} \cup \{X \mid \{W_4\} \subseteq X\} \\
 E^a\{W_3\} \{G \mid G \subseteq N\} &= \{X \mid \{W_1\} \subseteq X\} \\
 E^a\{W_4\} \{G \mid G \subseteq N\} &= \{X \mid \{W_2\} \subseteq X\} \\
 E^b\{W_1, W_2\} \{G \mid \{c, r\} \not\subseteq G\} &= \{X \mid \{W_3, W_4\} \subseteq X\} \\
 E^b\{W_1, W_2\} \{G \mid \{c, r\} \subseteq G\} &= \{X \mid \{W_3\} \subseteq X\} \cup \{X \mid \{W_4\} \subseteq X\} \\
 E^b\{W_3, W_4\} \{G \mid \{p\} \not\subseteq G\} &= \{X \mid \{W_1, W_2\} \subseteq X\} \\
 E^b\{W_3, W_4\} \{G \mid \{p\} \subseteq G\} &= \{X \mid \{W_1\} \subseteq X\} \cup \{X \mid \{W_2\} \subseteq X\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Truth in a Model. The truth of a CL formula in a given state s of such a coalition model M is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M, s &\not\models \perp \\
 M, s &\models p \quad \text{iff } p \in \Phi_0 \text{ and } s \in V(p) \\
 M, s &\models \varphi \wedge \psi \quad \text{iff } M, s \models \varphi \text{ and } M, s \models \psi \\
 M, s &\models \varphi \rightarrow \psi \quad \text{iff } M, s \models \varphi \Rightarrow M, s \models \psi \\
 M, s &\models [G]\varphi \quad \text{iff } \{s \in S \mid M, s \models \varphi\} \in E(s)(G)
 \end{aligned}$$

This translates into the following Lean definition:

```

1 def s_entails_CL {agents : Type} (m : modelCL agents) :
2   m.f.states → formCL agents → Prop
3   | s bot      := false
4   | s (var n) := s ∈ m.v n
5   | s (φ '→ ψ) := (s_entails_CL s φ) → (s_entails_CL s ψ)
6   | s (φ '∧ ψ) := (s_entails_CL s φ) ∧ (s_entails_CL s ψ)
7   | s ('[G] φ) := {t : m.f.states | s_entails_CL t φ} ∈
8     m.f.E.E (s) (G)
9 notation m `; ` s ` '⊥ ` φ := s_entails_CL m s φ
    
```

Here the first case (line 3) can be read as, in model m and state s , the truth value of the CL formula `bot` (\perp), is false. The second case (line 4) can be read as, in model m and state s , the n^{th} propositional variable is true in state s if s is in the set of states given by the model's valuation function `m.v (n)`.

Validity. Validity in a model, and global validity are defined as usual. φ is valid in a model (denoted as $M \models \varphi$), iff it is true in every state of the model. φ is globally valid (denoted as $\models \varphi$), iff it is valid in all models. These definitions are translated to Lean as follows:

```

1 def valid_m {agents: Type} (m : modelCL agents)
2   (φ : formCL agents) := ∀ s, m; s '⊨ φ
3 notation m ` '⊨ ` φ := valid_m m φ
4
    
```

```

5 def global_valid {agents: Type} (φ : formCL agents) :=
6   ∀ m, m '⊢ φ
7 notation `⊢` φ := global_valid φ

```

2.4 Axioms

CL is axiomatized under the following axioms **(Prop)** - **(S)** and rules **(MP)** - **(Eq)**:

(Prop) Propositional tautologies
 (\perp) $\vdash \neg[G]\perp$
 (\top) $\vdash [G]\top$
(N) $\vdash (\neg[\emptyset]\neg\varphi) \rightarrow [N]\varphi$
(M) $\vdash [G](\varphi \wedge \psi) \rightarrow [G]\varphi$
(S) $\vdash ([G]\varphi \wedge [F]\psi) \rightarrow [G \cup F](\varphi \wedge \psi)$, when $G \cap F = \emptyset$
(MP) $\vdash \varphi, \varphi \rightarrow \psi \Rightarrow \vdash \psi$
(Eq) $\vdash \varphi \leftrightarrow \psi \Rightarrow \vdash [G]\varphi \leftrightarrow [G]\psi$

In Lean the axiomatic system of CL is defined as an inductive predicate, or inductively defined proposition [4]. While an inductive type, like our `formCL` definition, is defined as the smallest type closed under a set of operators, an inductive predicate similarly is defined as the smallest predicate closed under a set of proof steps. Thus, where an inductive type contains all terms constructed by a finite tree of operator applications, an inductive predicate contains all proofs constructed from a finite tree of proof steps. This mirrors how the set of formulas provable in an axiomatic system is the smallest set closed under rule applications. Inductive predicates are thus a natural choice to define an axiomatic system.

For our axiomatic system we define `axCL`, where `axCL (φ)` can be read as $\vdash \varphi$. As we cannot define all instances of propositional tautologies in Lean, a small selection of axioms (`Prop1` - `Prop7`) were taken, as in Neeley's work [26]. All propositional tautologies of classical logic follow from these 7 axioms and MP [26].

```

1 inductive axCL {agents : Type} : formCL agents → Prop
2 | Prop1 {φ ψ} : axCL (φ '→ (ψ '→ φ))
3 | Prop2 {φ ψ χ} :
4   axCL ((φ '→ (ψ '→ χ)) '→ ((φ '→ ψ) '→ (φ '→ χ)))
5 | Prop3 {φ ψ} :
6   axCL (((¬φ) '→ (¬ψ)) '→ (((¬φ) '→ ψ) '→ φ))
7 | Prop4 {φ ψ} : axCL (φ '→ (ψ '→ (φ '∧ ψ)))
8 | Prop5 {φ ψ} : axCL ((φ '∧ ψ) '→ φ)
9 | Prop6 {φ ψ} : axCL ((φ '∧ ψ) '→ ψ)
10 | Prop7 {φ ψ} : axCL (((¬φ) '→ (¬ψ)) '→ (ψ '→ φ))
11 | Bot {G} : axCL ('¬ ('[G] '⊥))
12 | Top {G} : axCL ('[G] '⊤)
13 | N {φ} : axCL (('¬ ('[∅] ('¬ φ))) '→ '[univ] φ)
14 | M {φ ψ} {G} : axCL (('[G] (φ '∧ ψ)) '→ '[G] φ)
15 | S {φ ψ} {G F} (hInt : G ∩ F = ∅) :
16   axCL ((([G] φ) '∧ ([F] ψ)) '→ '[G ∪ F] (φ '∧ ψ))

```

```

17 | MP {ϕ ψ} (hImp : axCL (ϕ '→ ψ)) (hL : axCL ϕ) :
18   axCL (ψ)
19 | Eq {ϕ ψ} {G} (h : axCL (ϕ '↔ ψ)) :
20   axCL (( '[G] ϕ) '↔ (' [G] ψ))
21
22 prefix `!` : 70 := axCL

```

The first line states that we are defining an **inductive** predicate `axCL`. The output of our inductive predicate is a **Prop** which maps objects to truth values. A **Prop** is proof-irrelevant, meaning we cannot distinguish between two proofs of the same formula.

The first case (`Prop1`, on line 2) can be read as: for any formulas φ and ψ , the formula $\varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \varphi)$ is proven by the axiomatic system, thus $\vdash \varphi \rightarrow (\psi \rightarrow \varphi)$. In Lean terms, this means we can construct a term of the type `axCL (ϕ '→ (ψ '→ ϕ))`. Deduction rules are read very similarly, for instance case `MP` (lines 17-18), can be read as: for any formulas φ and ψ , given the term `axCL (ϕ '→ ψ)` and the term `(axCL ϕ)`, the term `axCL (ψ)` can be constructed. In other words, for any formulas φ and ψ , if $\vdash \varphi \rightarrow \psi$ and $\vdash \varphi$, then $\vdash \psi$.

Formulas as Type Classes in Lean. Many of the operators and axioms of CL relate only to propositional logic. Thus, the CL axioms prove many lemmas that are provable using only propositional logic. Intuitively, such lemmas are true in any logic that extends propositional logic, not just CL. In Lean we, therefore, aim to create a generic way to define and store all the necessary information to build propositional formulas and axiomatic proofs which can be reused for any such logic.

Specifically, we define a `Pformula` as a Lean **class**, given some logic's syntax, or more precisely some `form`: **Type**, for instance `formCL`, where the syntax of CL is defined. A Lean **class** is very similar to a Lean **structure**; our class simply contains the base atomic propositions and propositional operators. We choose to use the same operators as `formCL` for simplicity, with all propositional operators being defined as notation, leading to the following definition:

```

1 class Pformula (form : Type) :=
2   (bot : form)
3   (var : N → form)
4   (and : form → form → form)
5   (imp : form → form → form)
6
7 notation `!` : 80 := Pformula.bot
8 infix    `^` : 79 := Pformula.and
9 infixr  `>` : 78 := Pformula.imp
10 notation `¬` : 80 := λ ϕ, ϕ → !
11 notation `⊥` : 80 := ¬ !

```

```

12 infix   `∀` : 79 := λ φ ψ, (¬' φ) →' ψ
13 infix   `↔` : 78 := λ φ ψ, (φ →' ψ) ∧' (ψ →' φ)

```

The advantage of using a Lean **class** for `Pformula`, is that we can then create a Lean **instance** to demonstrate that `formCL` is a `Pformula`. Intuitively this can be thought of simply as proving `CL` contains the atomic propositions and operators of propositional logic. To do this we simply instantiate each of the atomic propositions and operators as follows:

```

1 instance formulaCLC {agents : Type} : Pformula (formCL agents) :=
2 { bot := formCL.bot,
3   var := formCL.var,
4   and := formCL.and,
5   imp := formCL.imp, }

```

If we then express some formula using our new **class** `Pformula`, Lean will know how to translate it to `CL` (or more specifically to `formCL`). In fact, the same applies for any `(form : Type)` that is an **instance** of **class** `Pformula`. Seeing as the syntax for our logic has to be deeply embedded and thus have its own syntax definitions, this is how we can create lemmas and definitions that are modular and reusable. For example, we can now define a finite conjunction as:

```

1 def finite_conjunction {form : Type} [pf : Pformula form] :
2   (list form) → form
3   | []           := T'
4   | (φ :: ψs)   := φ ∧' (finite_conjunction ψs)

```

This defines a finite conjunction for any `form : Type` that is an **instance** of the **class** `Pformula`, by using the `and` operator given in that **instance** (in our case `formCL.and`).

In the same way that we created a **class** for propositional formulas, we then create a **class** for the propositional axioms called `Pformula_ax`. To store these axioms we need to store first some function which tells us whether a formula can be proven by our axiomatic system. Then, this function must find that each of our axioms can indeed be proven by the axiomatic system.

This leads to the following **class** declaration:

```

1 class Pformula_ax (form : Type) extends Pformula form :=
2 (ax : form → Prop)
3 (p1 : ∀ φ ψ : form, ax (φ →' (ψ →' φ)))
4 (p2 : ∀ φ ψ χ : form, ax ((φ →' (ψ →' χ)) →' ((φ →' ψ) →' (φ →' χ))))
5 (p3 : ∀ φ ψ χ : form, ax (((¬' φ) →' (¬' ψ)) →' ((¬' φ) →' ψ) →' φ))
6 (p4 : ∀ φ ψ : form, ax (φ →' (ψ →' (φ ∧' ψ))))
7 (p5 : ∀ φ ψ : form, ax ((φ ∧' ψ) →' φ))
8 (p6 : ∀ φ ψ : form, ax ((φ ∧' ψ) →' ψ))
9 (p7 : ∀ φ ψ : form, ax (((¬' φ) →' (¬' ψ)) →' (ψ →' φ)))
10 (mp : ∀ φ ψ : form, ax (φ →' ψ) → ax φ → ax ψ)
11
12 prefix `⊢` : 70 := Pformula_ax.ax

```

Note that this class definition **extends** `Pformula form`, meaning that any instance of `Pformula_ax` must also be an instance of `Pformula`. Now, in Lean `Pformula_ax.ax (ψ)` means φ can be proven with the propositional axioms (`p1 - p7`) and rules (`mp`). Additionally, we can use those axioms and rules in the **class** `Pformula_ax`, to form proofs in any axiomatic system where those rules can be proven. For instance, the following lemma contains a proof for $\vdash \varphi \rightarrow \varphi$ for any `Pformula` :

```
1 lemma iden {form : Type} [pf : Pformula_ax form]
2   (ψ : form) : ⊢' (ψ →' ψ) :=
3   mp _ _ (mp _ _ (p2 ψ (ψ →' ψ) ψ) (p1 _ _)) (p1 _ _)
```

This proof can be translated to any syntax (or `form : Type`) with propositional operators where the propositional axioms hold, meaning it is an instance of `Pformula_ax`, and thus `Pformula`. The file `syntax/propLemmas.lean` includes many such propositional proofs.

We instantiate `Pformula_ax` for CL as follows:

```
1 instance formula_axCL {agents : Type} :
2   Pformula_ax (formCL agents) :=
3   { ax := axCL,
4     p1 := @axCL.Prop1 agents,
5     p2 := @axCL.Prop2 agents,
6     p3 := @axCL.Prop3 agents,
7     p4 := @axCL.Prop4 agents,
8     p5 := @axCL.Prop5 agents,
9     p6 := @axCL.Prop6 agents,
10    p7 := @axCL.Prop7 agents,
11    mp := @axCL.MP agents, }
```

Given this instance, we can now apply our previous lemma `iden` to some formula in our CL syntax (`ψ : formCL agents`)

```
1 lemma idenCL {agents : Type} (ψ : formCL agents) :
2   ⊢' (ψ →' ψ) := iden ψ
```

Next we create a generic `CLformula` which can be used for CL as well as extensions of CL. This time we combine the operators and axiomatic system for CL in one Lean **class**, as we will not be defining more complex types of formulas (like finite conjunctions) using the effectivity formulas. The Lean **class** `CLformula` is thus declared as follows:

```
1 class CLformula (agents : out_param Type) (form : Type)
2   [Pformula_ax form] :=
3   (eff : set agents → form → form)
4   (Bot : ∀ G, ⊢' (¬' (eff G ⊥)))
5   (Top : ∀ G, ⊢' (eff G ⊤))
6   (N : ∀ ψ : form, ⊢' ((¬' (eff ∅ (¬' ψ))) →' (eff univ ψ)))
7   (M : ∀ ψ ψ G, ⊢' ((eff G (ψ ∧' ψ)) →' (eff G ψ)))
8   (S : ∀ ψ ψ G F, G ∩ F = ∅ → ⊢' (((eff G ψ) ∧' (eff F ψ)) →'
```

```

9      (eff (G ∪ F) (ϕ ∧' ψ)))
10 (Eq : ∀ ϕ ψ G, ⊢' (ϕ ↔' ψ) → ⊢' ((eff G ϕ) ↔' (eff G ψ)))
11
12 notation `['` G ``]` : 80 ϕ := CLformula.eff G ϕ

```

Note that we specify that agents used in the class and `form`: **Type** must be the same. This can be seen in the hypothesis `(agents : out_param Type)`. In other words, for our definition of `CL`, the instance of `CLformula` should use the same `agents`: **Type** as used in the `formCL` `agents` definition.

Additionally, because `CL` extends propositional logic, we specify that if a Lean `form` : **Type** is a `CLformula`, it must be an instance of a `Pformula_ax`, and thus a `Pformula`. We therefore have access to all the propositional definitions and axioms defined by those Lean `classes`. We do not create an extension here, but represent this requirement by the hypothesis `[Pformula_ax form]` (line 2). We choose not to extend `Pformula_ax`, because it is preferable to not introduce new parameters when using `extends`, and in this instance we need to add `agents`. Additionally, we can extend propositional logic in multiple different ways, and those Logics can even be combined, for instance with `CL` and `EL` to make `CLC`. Using `extends` in Lean can get tricky if we try to combine multiple extensions, as we would need to demonstrate that both `Pformula_ax` instances are equal. Instead, by adding this requirement as a hypothesis, the same `Pformula_ax` instance can simply be passed up as needed.

Instantiating the `class` `CLformula` for our `formCL` syntax then again involves passing through the already defined operators and axioms. The code for this can be found in the file `syntax/syntaxCL.lean`.

Derived Axioms. The axiomatic system of `CL` allows us to derive one more important rule that will be used later.

Lemma 2 (Derived Monotonicity [29, Lemma 5.1]).

$$\vdash \varphi \rightarrow \psi \Rightarrow \vdash [G]\varphi \rightarrow [G]\psi$$

In Lean, we build this axiom for a **Type** that instantiates the generic `CLformula` class, so that the lemma is reusable for any logic which extends `CL`. Thus we define the lemma as follows:

```

1 def derived_monotonicity_rule {agents form : Type}
2   [pf : Pformula_ax form] [clf : CLformula agents form]
3   {ϕ ψ : form} {G : set agents} :
4   ⊢' (ϕ →' ψ) → ⊢' ((['G] ϕ) →' (['G] ψ)) :=

```

Proof. Again, we give a detailed proof along with its translation into Lean.

1. Assume $\vdash \varphi \rightarrow \psi$
2. $\vdash \varphi \rightarrow (\varphi \wedge \psi)$, from 1, by propositional logic
3. $\vdash ((\varphi \wedge \psi) \rightarrow \varphi)$, by propositional logic
4. $\vdash (\varphi \wedge \psi) \leftrightarrow \varphi$, from 2 & 3, by propositional logic

5. $\vdash [G](\varphi \wedge \psi) \leftrightarrow [G]\varphi$, from 4, by axiom **(Eq)**
6. $\vdash [G]\varphi \rightarrow [G](\varphi \wedge \psi)$, from 5, by propositional logic
7. $\vdash [G](\varphi \wedge \psi) \rightarrow [G](\psi)$, by axiom **(M)**
8. $\vdash [G]\varphi \rightarrow [G]\psi$, from 6 & 7, by propositional logic

This written proof corresponds to the following Lean proof.

```

1  intro h,
2  have h2 :  $\vdash (\varphi \rightarrow (\varphi \wedge \psi))$ , from imp_and_iden h,
3  have hp5 :  $\vdash ((\varphi \wedge \psi) \rightarrow \varphi)$ , from (p5 _ _),
4  have hiff :  $\vdash ((\varphi \wedge \psi) \leftrightarrow \varphi)$ , from MP' h2 (MP' hp5 (p4 _ _)),
5  have heq :  $\vdash (([G](\varphi \wedge \psi) \leftrightarrow [G]\varphi)$ , from (Eq _ _ _) hiff,
6  have hif :  $\vdash (([G]\varphi \rightarrow ([G](\varphi \wedge \psi)))$ , from iff_r heq,
7  have hM :  $\vdash (([G](\varphi \wedge \psi) \rightarrow [G]\psi)$ ,
8    from cut ef_and_switch (M _ _ _),
9  exact cut hif hM,

```

Steps 1-6 in the paper proof correspond directly to lines 1-6 of the Lean proof. Step 7 corresponds to the Lean lines 7 and 8, and finally step 8 of the paper proof is translated to line 9 in Lean.

Soundness.

Theorem 1 (Soundness of CL [29, Theorem 5.5]).

Proof. Trivially, we have $\vdash \varphi \Rightarrow \models \varphi$.

In Lean this theorem would be proven as follows :

```

1  theorem soundnessCL {agents : Type} (ϕ : formCL agents) :
2     $\vdash \varphi \rightarrow \models \varphi :=$ 
3  begin
4    intro h,
5    induction h,
6    -- case Prop1
7    { intros m s h1 h2,
8      exact h1, },
9    ...
10   -- case  $\perp$ 
11   { intros m s h1,
12     exact m.f.E.liveness s h h1, },
13   ...
14   -- case Eq
15   { intros m s,
16     have heq :  $\{t \mid m; t \models h_\varphi\} = \{t \mid m; t \models h_\psi\}$ , from
17       begin
18         apply set.ext,
19         intro u,
20         apply iff.intro,
21         { intro hu,

```

```

22         exact (h_ih m u).left hu, },
23     { intro hu,
24       exact (h_ih m u).right hu, },
25   end,
26   apply and.intro,
27   { intro h1,
28     simp only [s_entails_CL, ←heq] at *,
29     exact h1, },
30   { intro h1,
31     simp only [s_entails_CL, heq] at *,
32     exact h1, }, },
33 end

```

The proof is inductive on $\vdash \varphi$, so we have one case per rule or axiom. In the above code we include only the proofs for three of these cases. First we look at our first propositional axiom **Prop 1** (lines 5-7). We note that in this case, we aim to prove $\vDash \varphi \rightarrow \psi \rightarrow \varphi$. If we have $\vDash \varphi$ and $\vDash \psi$ (h1 and h2 in our code on line 6), we can trivially prove $\vDash \varphi$ (line 7). The other propositional cases are equally as trivial, and proved in a similar way by applying the appropriate hypotheses.

The next case included is the first axiom with the effectivity operator: axiom (\perp) (lines 9-11). Here we aim to prove $\vDash \neg[G]\perp$ (h1 in our code on line 10), meaning that given $\vDash [G]\perp$, we must prove a contradiction. This operator relates directly to the liveness playability condition, and thus we prove a contradiction by showing that $\vDash [G]\perp$ contradicts the liveness condition (line 11). The remaining cases, except for the axiom (**Eq**) function similarly, as they each relate directly to one of the playability conditions.

The proof for the axiom (**Eq**) case, simply requires us to show $\vDash [G]\phi \leftrightarrow [G]\psi$, given the induction hypothesis (ih): $\vDash \phi \leftrightarrow \psi$. We prove this by first using ih to prove that $\{s \in S \mid M, s \vDash \varphi\} = \{s \in S \mid M, s \vDash \psi\}$ (lines 15-24). This then allows us to quite trivially prove both sides of the iff statement (lines 25-34).

2.5 Completeness

Consistency. In order to prove completeness for CL, we will build a model where the states are maximally consistent sets of formulas. Thus, we must first define consistency, maximal consistency, and prove several lemmas about maximally consistent sets.

Definition 7 (Consistency). *A set of formulas Σ is consistent iff there are no $\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n \in \Sigma$ such that $\vdash (\sigma_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \sigma_n) \rightarrow \perp$.*

In Lean, we define consistency to apply to any formula that is an instance of a `Pformula_ax` Lean class. First we say that a set can prove a formula φ if the conjunction of (some of) its elements proves φ . In Lean, because we have defined a finite conjunction from a finite list of formulas, we thus need there to exist some list of formulas in the set, such that the conjunction of the list proves φ . Then, a consistent set of formulas Σ is defined as a set that does not prove \perp .

```

1 def set_proves {form : Type} [pf : Pformula_ax form]
2   (Γ : set (form)) (ψ : form) :=
3   ∃ (ψs : list (form)), (∀ ψ ∈ ψs, ψ ∈ Γ) ∧
4   ⊢' ((finite_conjunction ψs) →' ψ)
5
6 def ax_consistent {form : Type} [pf : Pformula_ax form]
7   (Γ : set form) : Prop :=
8   ¬ set_proves Γ ⊥'

```

Definition 8 (Maximal Consistency). *A maximally consistent set Σ is a consistent set such that all sets $\Sigma' \supset \Sigma$ are not consistent.*

This translates directly to the following Lean definition:

```

1 def max_ax_consistent {form : Type} [pf : Pformula_ax form]
2   (Γ : set form) : Prop :=
3   (ax_consistent Γ) ∧ (∀ Γ', Γ ⊂ Γ' → ¬ (ax_consistent Γ'))

```

Next, we prove several lemmas about consistency. These can be found in the file `syntax/consistency.lean`, but we describe two important lemmas now.

First, we show that for any maximally consistent set of formulas Σ , and any formula φ , $(\varphi \in \Sigma) \vee (\neg\varphi \in \Sigma)$. Our proof for this lemma is adapted from the work by Neeley [26] to apply to our `class` `Pformula_ax`.

```

1 lemma max_ax_contains_phi_or_neg {form : Type}
2   [pf : Pformula_ax form]
3   {Γ : set form} (hΓ : max_ax_consistent Γ) (ψ : form) :
4   ψ ∈ Γ ∨ (¬' ψ) ∈ Γ := ...

```

From the above lemma, we can prove that any maximally consistent set Σ proves any formula φ iff $\varphi \in \Sigma$. This relationship is particularly important to prove completeness, where we will need to use axiomatic proofs to determine the content of maximally consistent sets. It is easy to show that a set proves a member of its own set. In the other direction, we can use the `lemma` `max_ax_contains_phi_or_neg`, to either immediately prove $(\varphi \in \Sigma)$ or prove a contradiction if $(\neg\varphi \in \Sigma)$ and Σ proves φ . The full Lean proof can be found in the file `syntax/consistency.lean`.

```

1 lemma mem_max_consistent_iff_proves {form : Type}
2   [pf : Pformula_ax form]
3   {Γ : set (form)} (ψ : form) (hΓ : max_ax_consistent Γ) :
4   set_proves Γ ψ ↔ ψ ∈ Γ := ...

```

Canonical Model Construction. We show completeness of CL by constructing a canonical model M^C , such for each consistent CL formula φ , there is some state $s \in M^C$, where that formula holds: $M^C, s \models \varphi$.

We define the canonical model for CL as $M^C = (F^C, V^C)$, where $F^C = (S^C, E^C)$. First we define S^C as the set of all maximal CL-consistent set of formulas. In Lean, we call S^C `states` and define it as a `subtype`. A `subtype`

contains only those elements of some base **Type** that fulfill a certain property. In our case, we build a `subtype` as those sets of formulas that are maximally consistent.

```
1 def states (form : Type) [pf : Pformula_ax form] :=
2   {Γ : (set (form)) // (max_ax_consistent Γ)}
```

That `states` is not empty, follows from Lindenbaum's lemma [30], so this needs some setup in Lean. First we need Lindenbaum's lemma: that any consistent set can be extended into a maximally consistent set.

```
1 lemma lindenbaum {form : Type} [pf : Pformula_ax form]
2   {Γ : set form} (hax : ax_consistent Γ) :
3   ∃ Γ', max_ax_consistent Γ' ∧ Γ ⊆ Γ' := ...
```

We will not describe this proof (nor the proof for `max_ax_exists`, immediately following) in detail here as we mostly follow the work by Neeley [26] and the existing lemmas in the `mathlib` library [31], but the full proofs can be found in the file `syntax/consistency.lean`.

Given Lindenbaum's lemma, we can prove that S^C is nonempty (`lemma` `hs` in lines 17-23 below) if there exists any consistent sets of formulas. In turn, we prove the existence of such a set (`lemma` `max_ax_exists` in lines 13-15 below) given that the axiomatic system does not prove \perp (`lemma` `nprfalseCL` in lines 1-11 below).

```
1 lemma nprfalseCL {agents : Type} : ¬ ('⊥ : formCL agents) :=
2   begin
3     -- prove with the contrapositive of soundness : ¬ ⊢ ⊥
4     apply (mt (soundnessCL (@formCL.bot agents))),
5     -- assume by contradiction : ⊢ ⊥
6     intro hf,
7     -- ⊢ ⊥ only holds if no model with states exists
8     simp[global_valid, valid_m, s_entails_CL] at hf,
9     -- contradiction from an example single state model
10    exact hf (m_ex) single.one,
11  end
12
13 lemma max_ax_exists {form : Type} [pf : Pformula_ax form]
14   (hnprfalseCL : ¬ ⊢' (⊥' : form)) :
15   ∃ Γ : set form, max_ax_consistent Γ := ...
16
17 lemma hs (form : Type) [pf : Pformula_ax form]
18   (hnpr : ¬ ⊢' (⊥' : form)) : nonempty (states form) :=
19   begin
20     unfold states,
21     rw nonempty_subtype,
22     exact max_ax_exists hnpr,
23   end
```

Note that due to our use of the `class Pformula_ax` these lemmas, including Lindenbaum's lemma, have been proven for any logic that extends propositional logic. The only exception is `lemma nprfalseCL`, which uses an example model specific to CL.

Next, given S^C , E^C is built as follows:

$X \in E^C(s)(N)$ iff $\forall \varphi, \tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X^c \rightarrow [\emptyset]\varphi \notin s$, where $\tilde{\varphi} := \{t \in S^C \mid \varphi \in t\}$

$X \in E^C(s)(G)$ iff $\exists \varphi, \tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X \wedge [G]\varphi \in s$, when $G \neq N$

Informally, N can guarantee going to some world in X iff for all φ that are not in any world in X , φ is avoidable. Meanwhile, $G \subset N$ can guarantee going to some world in X iff the group is effective in bringing about some φ , where all worlds containing φ are in X .

In Lean we first define $\tilde{\varphi}$ as `tilde` given some `states : Type`. Note that here we are not explicitly referring to our defined `states`, allowing us to reuse this definition for any states we define. We do, however, specify that the `states : Type` must be `set_like` `states form` (line 3). For our purposes, this means that our states must contain formulas. The effectivity structure is then defined (lines 7-14) as a function with an `if-then-else` (or `ite`) condition.

```

1 def tilde {form : Type}
2   (states : Type) [sl : set_like states form]
3   (ψ : form) : set states :=
4   {s : states | ψ ∈ s}
5
6 def E {agents form : Type}
7   [pf : Pformula_ax form] [clf : CLformula agents form]
8   (s : states form) (G : set agents) :=
9   {X | ite (G = univ)
10  -- condition G = N
11  (∀ ψ, tilde (states form) ψ ⊆ Xc → ([∅] ψ) ∉ s)
12  -- condition G ≠ N
13  (∃ ψ, tilde (states form) ψ ⊆ X ∧ ([G] ψ) ∈ s)}

```

Lastly, to construct M^C , V^C is defined as usual, such that $s \in V^C(p)$ iff $p \in s$. In Lean the valuation function is defined based on the number n the variable $p \in \Phi_0$ is indexed to.

```

1 v := λ n, {s | (Pformula.var n) ∈ s}

```

Playability of the Canonical Model. We prove that M^C meets the requirements for being a coalition model, by showing that E^C is playable [29, Lemma 5.2]. Based on Lemma 1, we do this by showing that E^C is semi-playable, regular and N-maximal. The Lean proofs for semi-playability, N-maximality and regularity follow the written proof as closely as possible. For space only the proof for semi-playable liveness is included, due to this proof requiring some more complex consistency lemmas. The full Lean proof can be found in file `completeness/canonical.lean`.

1. $E^C(s)$ is live for all $G \subset N$. $\forall G \subset N : \emptyset \notin E^C(s)(G)$.
 - 1.1. Consider any $G \subset N$.
 - 1.2. Assume towards contradiction that $\emptyset \in E^C(s)(G)$.
 - 1.3. Consider some φ such that $\tilde{\varphi} \subseteq \emptyset$ and $[G]\varphi \in s$, which exists by 1.2 and definition of E^C .
 - 1.4. $\vdash \varphi \leftrightarrow \perp$, because $\{\varphi\}$ cannot be extended into a maximally consistent set (by 1.3), so $\{\varphi\}$ must be inconsistent.
 - 1.5. $\vdash [G]\varphi \leftrightarrow [G]\perp$, from 1.4, by axiom (**Eq**).
 - 1.6. $[G]\perp \in s$, from 1.5 and 1.3.
 - 1.7. Contradiction from axiom (\perp): $\neg[G]\perp$ and 1.6.

Translating that to Lean we have:

```

1 lemma semi_liveness {agents form : Type}
2   [pf : Pformula_ax form] [clf : CLformula agents form]
3   (s : states form) {G : set agents} (hG : G ⊂ univ) :
4   ∅ ∉ E (s) (G) :=
5 begin
6   -- Assume towards contradiction that ∅ ∈ E(s)(G)
7   unfold E,
8   intros hf,
9
10  -- ∃ψ̃ ⊆ ∅ : [G]ψ ∈ s, from hf, by definition of EC
11  simp [ne_of_ssubset hG] at hf,
12  cases hf with ψ hψ,
13
14  -- ⊢ ψ ↔ ⊥, because {ψ} cannot be extended into a max
15  -- consistent set (by hf), so {ψ} must be inconsistent.
16  have hiffbot : ⊢' (ψ ↔' ⊥'),
17    from set_empty_iff_false hψ.left,
18
19  -- ⊢ [G]ψ ↔ [G]⊥, from hiffbot, by axiom (Eq)
20  have hiffGbot : ⊢' (([G] ψ) ↔' ([G] ⊥)),
21    from Eq _ _ _ hiffbot,
22
23  -- [G]⊥ ∈ s, from hψ and hiffGbot.
24  have h : ([G] ⊥) ∈ s,
25    from by apply max_ax_contains_by_set_proof s.2 hψ.right
26      (iff_l hiffGbot),
27
28  -- Contradiction from axiom (⊥) : ¬[G]⊥ and h
29  apply ax_neg_contains_pr_false s.2 h (Bot _),
30 end

```

We will take a closer look at step 1.4 (lines 14-17), because here lemma `set_empty_iff_false` is doing the interesting work, so we will expand a little on how it works. All the full lemmas used to prove `set_empty_iff_false` can be found in `syntax/consistency.lean`.

First we define the lemma `false_of_always_false`:

```

1 lemma false_of_always_false {form : Type}
2   [pf : Pformula_ax form] (ψ : form)

```

```

3   (h : ∀ Γ (hΓ : max_ax_consistent Γ), ¬ set_proves Γ φ) :
4   ⊢ (¬ φ) :=
5   begin
6     let Γ := {φ},
7     by_cases hψ : ax_consistent Γ,
8     ...
9   end

```

This lemma states that if all maximally consistent sets do not prove φ , then $\vdash \neg\varphi$. The proof for this lemma is done by splitting on whether $\{\varphi\}$ is consistent. If $\{\varphi\}$ is consistent then there must be a maximally consistent set which contains and therefore proves φ , contradicting the hypothesis. If $\{\varphi\}$ is not consistent then this set must prove false, so we must have $\vdash \neg\varphi$. From this lemma we can prove that if φ is not in any maximally consistent set, then $\vdash \varphi \leftrightarrow \perp$:

```

1   lemma false_of_always_false' {form : Type}
2     [pf : Pformula_ax form] (ψ : form)
3     (h : ∀ (Γ : set (form)) (hΓ : max_ax_consistent Γ), ψ ∉ Γ) :
4     ⊢ (ψ ↔ '⊥') := ...

```

This proof is relatively trivial by propositional logic, `false_of_always_false'`, and our earlier proof `mem_max_consistent_iff_proves` that maximally consistent sets contain some formula ψ iff the set proves ψ . Finally, we use `false_of_always_false'` to prove `set_empty_iff_false`: if the set of all maximally consistent sets containing φ is empty, then $\vdash \varphi \leftrightarrow \perp$.

```

1   lemma set_empty_iff_false {form : Type}
2     [pf : Pformula_ax form] {ψ : form}
3     (hempty : {Γ : {Γ : set form | max_ax_consistent Γ} |
4       ψ ∈ Γ.val} ⊆ ∅) :
5     ⊢ (ψ ↔ '⊥') :=
6   begin
7     refine false_of_always_false' ψ (λ Γ hΓ h, hempty _),
8     { exact ⟨Γ, hΓ⟩ },
9     { exact h },
10  end

```

2. $E^c(s)$ is safe for all $G \subset N$. $\forall G \subset N : S^c \in E^c(s)(G)$.
 - 2.1. Consider any $G \subset N$.
 - 2.2. $[G]\top \in s$ and $\tilde{\top} = S^c$, from axiom (T): $[G]\top$, and definition of S^c .
 - 2.3. $\exists \varphi, \tilde{\varphi} \subseteq S^c \wedge [G]\varphi \in s$, where $\varphi = \top$ from 2.2.
 - 2.4. $S^c \in E^c(s)(G)$, from 2.3, by definition of E^c .
3. $E^c(s)$ is outcome monotonic for all $G \subset N$:
 $\forall G \subset N, \forall X \subseteq Y \subseteq S^c : X \in E^c(s)(G) \Rightarrow Y \in E^c(s)(G)$.
 - 3.1. Consider any $G \subset N$ and $X \subseteq Y \subseteq S^c$, such that $X \in E^c(s)(G)$.
 - 3.2. Consider some $\tilde{\varphi}$ such that $\tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X$ and $[G]\tilde{\varphi} \in s$, which exists by 3.1 and definition of E^c .
 - 3.3. $\tilde{\varphi} \subseteq Y : [G]\tilde{\varphi} \in s$, because $\tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X \subseteq Y$, from 3.1 and 3.2.
 - 3.4. $Y \in E^c(s)(G)$, from 3.3, by definition of E^c .
4. $E^c(s)$ is superadditive for all $G \cup F \subset N$:
 $\forall G, F \subset N$ (where $G \cap F = \emptyset$ and $G \cup F \subset N$), $\forall X, Y \subseteq S^c : X \in E^c(s)(G)$ and $Y \in E^c(s)(F) \Rightarrow X \cap Y \in E^c(s)(G \cup F)$.

- 4.1. Consider any $G, F \subseteq N$ (where $G \cap F = \emptyset$ and $G \cup F \subseteq N$) and any $X, Y \subseteq S^c$, such that $X \in E^c(s)(G)$ and $Y \in E^c(s)(F)$.
 - 4.2. Consider some φ such that $\tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X$ and $[G]\varphi \in s$, and some ψ such that $\tilde{\psi} \subseteq Y$ and $[F]\psi \in s$, which both exist by 4.1 and definition of E^c .
 - 4.3. $[G \cup F](\varphi \wedge \psi) \in s$, from 4.1 and 4.2, by axiom **(S)**: $([G]\varphi \wedge [F]\psi) \rightarrow [G \cup F](\varphi \wedge \psi)$.
 - 4.4. $\varphi \wedge \psi \subseteq X \cap Y : [G \cup F](\varphi \wedge \psi) \in s$, from 4.2 and 4.3.
 - 4.5. $(X \cap Y) \in E^c(s)(G \cup F)$, from 4.4, by definition of E^c .
 5. From 1, 2, 3, and 4 we have semi-playability.
 6. $E^c(s)$ is regular: $\forall G \subseteq N, \forall X \subseteq S^c : X \in E^c(s)(G) \Rightarrow X^c \notin E^c(s)(G^c)$.
 - 6.1. case: $G = N$:
 - 6.1.1. Consider any $X \subseteq S^c$, such that $X \in E^c(s)(N)$.
 - 6.1.2. $\forall \varphi, \tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X^c \rightarrow [\emptyset]\varphi \notin s$, from 6.1.1, by definition of E^c .
 - 6.1.3. $\neg(\exists \varphi, \tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X^c \wedge [\emptyset]\varphi \in s)$, from 6.1.2, by first order logic.
 - 6.1.4. $\neg(X^c \in E^c(s)(\emptyset))$, from 6.1.3, by definition of E^c .
 - 6.1.5. $X^c \notin E^c(s)(\emptyset)$, from 6.1.4.
 - 6.2. case: $G = \emptyset$:
 - 6.2.1. Consider any $X \subseteq S^c$, such that $X \in E^c(s)(\emptyset)$.
 - 6.2.2. $\exists \varphi, \tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X \wedge [\emptyset]\varphi \in s$, from 6.2.1, by definition of E^c .
 - 6.2.3. $\neg(\forall \varphi, \tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X \rightarrow [\emptyset]\varphi \notin s)$, from 6.2.2, by first order logic.
 - 6.2.4. $\neg(X^c \in E^c(s)(N))$, from 6.2.3, by definition of E^c .
 - 6.2.5. $X^c \notin E^c(s)(N)$, from 6.2.4.
 - 6.3. case: $G \neq N$ and $G^c \neq N$:
 - 6.3.1. Consider any $X \subseteq S^c$, such that $X \in E^c(s)(G)$.
 - 6.3.2. Consider some φ , such that $\tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X \wedge [G]\varphi \in s$, which exists by 6.3.1 and definition of E^c .
 - 6.3.3. Assume towards a contradiction that $X^c \in E^c(s)(G^c)$.
 - 6.3.4. Consider some ψ such that $\tilde{\psi} \subseteq X^c \wedge [G^c]\psi \in s$, which exists by 6.3.3 and definition of E^c .
 - 6.3.5. $[G \cup G^c](\varphi \wedge \psi) \in s$, from 6.3.2 and 6.3.4, by axiom **(S)** $[G]\varphi \wedge [G^c]\psi \rightarrow [G \cup G^c](\varphi \wedge \psi) \in s$.
 - 6.3.6. $(\varphi \wedge \psi) = \emptyset$, from 6.3.2 and 6.3.4 because X and X^c are disjoint, meaning $\tilde{\varphi}$ and $\tilde{\psi}$ are disjoint.
 - 6.3.7. $\vdash (\varphi \wedge \psi) \leftrightarrow \perp$, because $\{(\varphi \wedge \psi)\}$ cannot be extended into a maximally consistent set (by 6.3.6), so $\{(\varphi \wedge \psi)\}$ must be inconsistent.
 - 6.3.8. $\vdash [N](\varphi \wedge \psi) \leftrightarrow [N]\perp$, from 6.3.7, by axiom **(Eq)**.
 - 6.3.9. $[N]\perp \in s$, from 6.3.8 and 6.3.5.
 - 6.3.10. Contradiction from axiom **(\perp)**: $\neg[N]\perp$ and 6.3.9.
7. $E^c(s)$ is N-Maximal: $\forall X \subseteq S^c : X^c \notin E^c(s)(\emptyset) \Rightarrow X \in E^c(s)(N)$.
 - 7.1. Consider any $X \subseteq S$, such that $X^c \notin E^c(s)(\emptyset)$.
 - 7.2. $\neg X^c \in E^c(s)(\emptyset)$, from 7.1.
 - 7.3. $\neg \exists \varphi, \tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X^c \wedge [\emptyset]\varphi \in s$, from 7.2, by definition of E^c .
 - 7.4. $\forall \varphi, \tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X^c \rightarrow [\emptyset]\varphi \notin s$, from 7.3, by first order logic.
 - 7.5. $X \in E^c(s)(N)$, from 7.4, by definition of E^c .

In we Lean we can now use all these definitions and lemmas to instantiate the `structure frameCL` and the `structure modelCL`:

```

1 def canonical_frame_CL (agents form : Type) [ha : nonempty agents]
2   [pf : Pformula_ax form] clf : CLformula agents form]
3   (hnpr : ¬ ⊢' ⊥') : frameCL agents :=
4   { states := states form,
5     hs := hs form hnpr,
6     E :=
7       begin
8         let semi : semi_playable_effectivity_struct
9           agents (states form) :=
10          { E := E,
11            semi_liveness := semi_liveness,
12            semi_safety := semi_safety,
13            semi_mono := semi_mono,
14            semi_superadd := semi_superadd, },
15
16          exact playable_from_semi_Nmax_reg (states form) semi
17            N_maximality regularity,
18        end, }
19
20 def canonical_model_CL (agents form : Type) [ha : nonempty agents]
21   [pf : Pformula_ax form] [clf : CLformula agents form]
22   (hnpr : ¬ ⊢' (⊥' : form)) : modelCL agents :=
23   { f := canonical_frame_CL agents form hnpr,
24     v := λ n, {s | (Pformula.var n) ∈ s} }

```

Note, that the canonical model is defined using our generic `class` `Pformula_ax` and `class` `CLformula`, meaning that we can reuse these definitions later for CLC (and any other logic that extends CL).

Truth Lemma. Next we show that the canonical model is defined in such a way that the formulas contained in each state are also true in that state.

Lemma 3 (CL Truth Lemma [29, Lemma 5.3]). *A formula is true in a world in S^C iff it is contained by that world. $\forall s \in S^C, M^C, s \models \varphi$ iff $\varphi \in s$.*

In Lean we prove:

```

1 lemma truth_lemma_CL {agents : Type} [ha : nonempty agents]
2   (ψ : formCL agents) (s : (M_CL agents).f.states) :
3   ((M_CL agents); s '⊨ ψ) ↔ (ψ ∈ s) :=

```

The full Lean proof can be found in file `completeness/completenessCL.lean`.

Proof. This proof is by induction on φ . The cases for atomic propositions and propositional operators are straightforward from the fact that s is maximally consistent. We focus here on the case $[G]\varphi$:

1. Have induction hypothesis (IH): $M^C, s \models \varphi$ iff $\varphi \in s$.
2. It is sufficient to consider the case when $G \subset N$,
because $\vdash [N]\varphi \leftrightarrow \neg[\emptyset]\neg\varphi$.

- ⇒ 2.1. Assume $[N]\varphi$.
- 2.2. Assume towards a contradiction $[\emptyset]\neg\varphi$.
- 2.3. $[N](\varphi \wedge \neg\varphi)$, from 2.1 and 2.2, by axiom **(S)**: $([N]\varphi \wedge [\emptyset]\neg\varphi) \rightarrow [N \cup \emptyset](\varphi \wedge \neg\varphi)$.
- 2.4. $[N](\perp)$, from 2.3, by axiom **(Eq)**: $(\varphi \wedge \neg\varphi) \leftrightarrow (\perp) \Rightarrow [N](\varphi \wedge \neg\varphi) \leftrightarrow [N](\perp)$ and propositional logic.
- 2.5. Contradiction from axiom **(\perp)**: $\neg[N]\perp$ and 2.4.
- ⇐ by axiom **(N)**.
- 3. $M^c, s \models [G]\varphi \Rightarrow [G]\varphi \in s$, when $G \subset N$.
 - 3.1. Assume $M^c, s \models [G]\varphi$.
 - 3.2. $\{s \in S^c \mid M^c, s \models \varphi\} \in E(s)(G)$, from 3.1, by definition of \models .
 - 3.3. Consider some ψ such that $\psi \subseteq \{t \in S^c \mid M^c, t \models \varphi\} \wedge [G]\psi \in s$, which exists by 3.2 and definition of E^c .
 - 3.4. $\tilde{\psi} \subseteq \{t \in S^c \mid M^c, \varphi \in t\} \wedge [G]\psi \in s$, from 3.3, by IH.
 - 3.5. $\psi \subseteq \tilde{\varphi} \wedge [G]\psi \in s$, from 3.4.
 - 3.6. $\vdash \psi \rightarrow \varphi$, since $\psi \subseteq \tilde{\varphi}$ in 3.5.
 - 3.7. $\vdash [G]\psi \rightarrow [G]\varphi$, from 3.6, by the derived monotonicity rule.
 - 3.8. $[G]\varphi \in s$, from 3.7 and 3.5.
- 4. $[G]\varphi \in s \Rightarrow M^c, s \models [G]\varphi$, when $G \subset N$.
 - 4.1. Assume $[G]\varphi \in s$.
 - 4.2. $\tilde{\varphi} \subseteq \{t \in S^c \mid \varphi \in t\} : [G]\varphi \in s$, from 4.1.
 - 4.3. $\{t \in S^c \mid \varphi \in t\} \in E^c(s)(G)$, from 4.2, by definition of $E^c(s)(G)$.
 - 4.4. $\{t \in S^c \mid M^c, t \models \varphi\} \in E(s)(G)$, from 4.3, by IH.
 - 4.5. $M^c, s \models [G]\varphi$, from 4.4, by definition of \models .

Completeness.

Theorem 2 (Completeness of CL[29, Theorem 5.5]). $\forall \varphi, \models \varphi \Rightarrow \vdash \varphi$

Proof. We prove the contrapositive by showing that every CL consistent formula exists in some state in S^c , and by Lemma 3 is also true in that state.

1. Taking the contrapositive we aim to show $\not\models \varphi \Rightarrow \not\vdash \varphi$.
2. Assume $\neg \vdash \varphi$.
3. $\{\neg\varphi\}$ is a consistent set, from 2.
4. With Lindenbaum's lemma, $\{\neg\varphi\}$ can be extended into a maximally consistent set Σ .
5. Take the state $s \in S^c$, where $s = \Sigma$. Note that $\neg\varphi \in s$.
6. We prove that φ is not globally valid, by proving that $M^c, s \not\models \varphi$.
 - 6.1. Assume towards a contradiction that $M^c, s \models \varphi$.
 - 6.2. $\varphi \in s$, by lemma 3, from 6.1.
 - 6.3. Contradiction from 5 & 6.2.

This proof again translates fairly directly into Lean. The full Lean proof can be found in the file `completeness/completenessCL.lean`.

```

1 theorem completenessCL {agents : Type} [ha : nonempty agents]
2   (ψ : formCL agents) : ('⊨ ψ) → '⊢ ψ := ...

```

With this proof we have fully implemented the syntax and semantics of CL in Lean and verified these definitions by proving both soundness and completeness.

3 Formalizing Coalition Logic with Common Knowledge in Lean

The addition of knowledge operators is a natural extension to logics such as CL, that aim to describe the behavior of coalitions of agents. Different agents are likely to possess varying levels of knowledge and may not have access to precisely the same information at all times [15]. In our light-bulb example (Figure 2) for instance, the controller may not always know if the light-bulb is on or off due to not being physically connected to the device. It is easy to come up with other examples: in card games players might only know their own hand, one train might have more knowledge about its own functioning than about the functioning of other trains, and a traffic light and a car may know the traffic in different locations. As well as providing a more accurate framework to describe these kind of scenarios, extending CL with knowledge operators allows us to express and examine new and interesting properties of MAS. For instance, there may be a difference between a coalition being able to achieve some goal, and everyone in the coalition knowing that the goal can be achieved.

Ågotnes and Alechina [1] extend CL into CLC by simply adding the epistemic operators for individual and common knowledge. Here the individual knowledge operator $K_i\varphi$, where $i \in N$ is an agent, represents that i knows φ . Common knowledge on the other hand is a type of group knowledge: $C_G\varphi$ means that every agent in the group $G \subseteq N$ knows φ , and every agent in G knows that every agent in G knows φ , and every agent in G knows that every agent in G knows that every agent in G knows φ , and so on. In this section we will follow the work of Ågotnes and Alechina [1] to define CLC in Lean. We formally define the syntax of CLC in Section 3.1. Following this we will formalize the semantics, and axioms of CLC in Lean in Sections 3.2 & 3.3 respectively. Finally, using these definitions we will prove in Lean that CLC is complete in Section 3.4.

3.1 Syntax

Given a finite, non-empty set of agents N , and a set of atomic propositions Φ_0 , a CLC formula is constructed from the usual propositional logic operators, the CL effectivity operator $[G]\varphi$, where $G \subseteq N$, and two epistemic operators: individual and common knowledge. The operator K_i , is used to model the knowledge of one agent $i \in N$. Thus $K_i\varphi$ can be intuitively read as “agent i knows φ ”. This individual knowledge can be extended to groups by simply using the conjunction of individual knowledge. Thus, the operator $E_G\varphi$, read as “everyone in group $G \subseteq N$ knows φ ”, is defined as $E_G\varphi := \bigwedge_{i \in G} K_i\varphi$.

Common knowledge on the other hand, refers not only to the conjunction of individual knowledge, but also knowledge about the groups knowledge. A group G has common knowledge of some φ , iff every agent in G knows φ and they all know that they all know φ , and they all know that they all know that they all know φ and so on. The common knowledge operator $C_G\varphi$, can be intuitively read as “ φ is common knowledge to group $G \subseteq N$ ”. CLC is thus defined by the following BNF grammar:

$$\varphi := \perp \mid p \mid \varphi \wedge \varphi \mid \varphi \rightarrow \varphi \mid [G]\varphi \mid K_i\varphi \mid C_G\varphi$$

where $p \in \Phi_0$, $G \subseteq N$ and $i \in N$. We note here that our syntax here is slightly different from that of Ågotnes and Alechina [1], as we allow the case when $G = \emptyset$ for the $C_G\varphi$ operator. Note that intuitively $C_\emptyset\varphi$ can be read as: everyone in \emptyset knows φ , and they all know that they all know φ and so on; which must always be true. $C_\emptyset\varphi$ is thus not very modally interesting. We include it in order to generalise our definition of common knowledge by removing the requirement $G \neq \emptyset$. Changing our syntax in this way means we will not be required to check that $G \neq \emptyset$, before we can make a statement about the common knowledge of G , nor will we need to add $G \neq \emptyset$ as a hypothesis for future lemmas or definitions, simplifying them slightly. Allowing $C_\emptyset\varphi$ still results in our defined logic being both sound and complete, and it is easy to add the requirement in future work if needed.

In Lean, the syntax for CLC is defined as in CL, but with the additional operators included:

```

1 inductive formCLC (agents : Type) : Type
2 ...
3 | K (a : agents) (ψ : formCLC) : formCLC
4 | C (G : set agents) (ψ : formCLC) : formCLC

```

From this definition we can immediately show that CLC extends the propositional syntax by instantiating our `class Pformula`. This allows us to use the previously defined `finite_conjunction`, to define the remaining operator: $E_G\varphi$. It is important to note, that this is the first time that we explicitly require N to be finite. If N is infinite we cannot guarantee that $E_G\varphi := \bigwedge_{i \in G} K_i\varphi$ results in a finite formula. In Lean we ensure that a `finite_conjunction` is indeed finite, by requiring the input to be a `list`; a finite data structure in Lean. We therefore have to convert our set G , which we know is finite because N is finite, into a list. This conversion happens in line 7 below, luckily using inbuilt functions from the `mathlib` library [31]. First we determine that G must be finite because N is finite, with `(finite.of_fintype G)`. This part is particularly important, as it requires us to specify that our `agents : Type` is finite from now on if we use the $E_G\varphi$ operator. Given that G is finite, we next determine that it is a finite set. This sounds trivial, but in Lean a finite set is its own distinct data structure, so we use `finite.to_finset` to convert our set G into a finite set (or a `finset`). Finally, the `finset` data structure, knows that a finite set can be converted into a list, and does this with the `finset.to_list` function. The order of this list is arbitrary, but this did not lead to problems in the proof.

```

1 instance formulaCLC {agents : Type} : Pformula (formCLC agents) :=
2 { bot := formCLC.bot, ... }
3
4 notation `K` : ?? := formCLC.K
5 notation `E` : ?? :=
6   λ G ψ, (finite_conjunction (list.map (λ i, 'K i ψ)

```

```

7     (finset.to_list (finite.to_finset (finite.of_fintype G))))
8 notation `C` : 77 := formCLC.C

```

It is clear from defining the $E_G\varphi$ operator, that working with finite sets in Lean adds a layer of complexity that is not present in a paper proof. Although our implementation choice is not the only approach, the inflexibility of data structures in Lean means that there will always be added complexity when converting between them. Using these definitions for related proofs is thus particularly interesting.

3.2 Semantics

Frames and models for CLC are called epistemic coalition frames and models. They differ from coalition frames and models in two main ways. First, an epistemic coalition model contains an epistemic accessibility relation for each agent. These equivalence relations model what each agent does and does not know. Specifically $s \sim_i t$ (shorthand for $(s, t) \in \sim_i$) indicates that agent i cannot differentiate world s and world t . These epistemic accessibility relations suffice for both knowledge operators: common knowledge is represented by a path of epistemic operators: $(\bigcup_{i \in G} \sim_i)^*$, where R^* refers to the transitive closure of R .

The second difference between coalition and epistemic coalition frames is in regards to their effectivity structures. In an epistemic coalition frame, this structure must be truly playable, rather than just playable.

Definition 9 (True Playability). *A truly playable effectivity structure is any effectivity structure E , such that for any state s , $E(s)$ meets all 5 Playability conditions (Section 2.1, Definition 2) and:*

$$6. E(s)(\emptyset) \text{ is principal. } \exists X \in E(s)(\emptyset), \forall Y \in E(s)(\emptyset), X \subseteq Y$$

Importantly, playability and true playability only differ in infinite domains [14, Corollary 1]. That is, in finite domains, given that E is a playable effectivity structure, $E(s)(\emptyset)$ must be principal. We know that $E(s)(\emptyset)$ is nonempty by safety, so in a finite domain $E(s)(\emptyset)$ must have minimal elements. We then can prove that there is only one minimum element, because if there were two minimal elements X and Y , by superadditivity $(X \cap Y) \in E(s)(\emptyset)$, and thus $X = Y$.

In Lean we define true playability by extending

`playable_effectivity_struct`. Extending a Lean `structure` data type simply means adding some elements. In our case we add one hypothesis relating to our new requirement:

```

1 structure truly_playable_effectivity_struct (agents states : Type)
2   extends playable_effectivity_struct agents states :=
3   (principal_E_s_empty : ∀ s, ∃ X, X ∈ E s ∅ ∧ ∀ Y, Y ∈ E s ∅ → X ⊆ Y)

```

We then define a function that, if S is finite, creates a `truly_playable_effectivity_struct` from a `playable_effectivity_struct`. Our above paper proof translates pretty directly into Lean. Note that we only prove the condition `principal_E_s_empty`

(lines 5-27), as we meet the other conditions from assuming playability (lines 3 & 28) The full Lean proof can be found in the file `semantics/playability.lean`.

```

1  def truly_playable_from_finite {agents states : Type}
2    [hS : fintype states]
3    (play : playable_effectivity_struct agents states) :
4    truly_playable_effectivity_struct agents states :=
5    { principal_E_s_empty :=
6      begin
7        intro s,
8        -- E (s) (∅) is nonempty by safety
9        have hnotEmpty : (finite.to_finset (finite.of_fintype
10         (play.E s ∅))).nonempty, from
11         begin
12           ...
13           exact play.safety s ∅,
14         end,
15        -- if S is finite, E (s) (∅) must have some minimal elements
16        have hminimal :=
17          finset.exists_minimal (finite.to_finset (finite.of_fintype
18           (play.E s ∅))) hnotEmpty,
19        ...
20        { -- If there were two minimal elements X and Y
21          intros Y hY,
22          -- by superadditivity (X ∩ Y) ∈ E (s) (∅), and thus X = Y.
23          cases em (X = Y),
24          { exact eq.subset h, },
25          { have hun := play.superadd s _ _ _ _ hX hY (empty_inter ∅),
26            ... }, },
27        end,
28      .. play }

```

With these two changes from coalition frames, epistemic coalition frames and models are defined as follows:

Definition 10 (Epistemic Coalition Frame). *An epistemic coalition frame is a tuple*

$F = (S, E, \{\sim_i : i \in N\})$, *where:*

S *is a non-empty set of states*

$E : S \rightarrow (\mathcal{P}(N) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{P}(S)))$ *is a **truly** playable effectivity structure*

$\sim_i \subseteq S \times S$ *is an epistemic equivalence relation over S for agent i*

Definition 11 (Epistemic Coalition Model). *An epistemic coalition model is a tuple $M = (F, V)$, where:*

F *is an epistemic coalition frame*

$V : \Phi_0 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(S)$ *is the usual valuation function, assigning a set $V(s) \subseteq \Phi_0$ to each state $s \in S$*

In Lean these definitions translate to:

```

1 structure frameECL (agents : Type) :=
2   (states      : Type)
3   (hs         : nonempty states)
4   (E         : truly_playable_effectivity_struct agents states)
5   (rel       : agents → states → set states)
6   (rfl      : ∀ i s, s ∈ (rel i s))
7   (sym      : ∀ i s t, t ∈ (rel i s) → s ∈ (rel i t))
8   (trans    : ∀ i s t u, t ∈ (rel i s) → u ∈ (rel i t) →
9             u ∈ (rel i s))
10
11 structure modeleCL (agents : Type) :=
12   (f : frameECL agents)
13   (v : ℕ → set f.states)

```

Formally Describing Two Example Epistemic Coalition Models. Having formally defined epistemic coalition models, we can quickly finish the formal definition example models in Figure 2. Our previously defined effectivity structure is truly playable, so we only need to add our epistemic relations to our existing definition in 2.3. On top of reflexive relations we only add $W_3 \sim_c W_4$ and $W_4 \sim_c W_3$ to model 2a and $W_1 \sim_c W_2$ and $W_2 \sim_c W_1$ to model 2b.

Truth in a Model. To determine truth of a CLC formula in a given state s of an epistemic coalition model M , we need to account for the two new epistemic operators. $K_i\varphi$ relates very intuitively to the \sim_i relation: if agent i knows φ , it must be true in all the worlds i might be in. The operator $C_G\varphi$ is a little more complex, as here we need to consider a “path” through epistemic relations: $(\bigcup_{i \in G} \sim_i)^*$. For readability we write $(s, t) \in (\bigcup_{i \in G} \sim_i)^*$ as $s \approx_G t$. Thus, truth in an epistemic coalition model is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
M, s &\not\models \perp \\
M, s &\models p && \text{iff } p \in \Phi_0 \text{ and } s \in V(p) \\
M, s &\models \varphi \wedge \psi && \text{iff } M, s \models \varphi \text{ and } M, s \models \psi \\
M, s &\models \varphi \rightarrow \psi && \text{iff } M, s \models \varphi \Rightarrow M, s \models \psi \\
M, s &\models [G]\varphi && \text{iff } \{s \in S \mid M, s \models \varphi\} \in E(s)(G) \\
M, s &\models K_i\varphi && \text{iff } \forall t \in S, s \sim_i t \Rightarrow M, t \models \varphi \\
M, s &\models C_G\varphi && \text{iff } \forall t \in S, s \approx_G t \Rightarrow M, t \models \varphi,
\end{aligned}$$

In Lean we first define this common knowledge “path” as a recursively defined predicate that we call a `C_path`.

```

1 def C_path {agents : Type} {m : modeleCL agents} :
2   list agents → list m.f.states → m.f.states → m.f.states →
3   Prop
4   | list.nil _ s t := false
5   | (i :: is) list.nil s t := t ∈ (m.f.rel i s)
6   | (i :: is) (u :: us) s t := (u ∈ (m.f.rel i s) ∧
7                                 (C_path is us u t))

```

Intuitively, we say that there is a path from world s to world t , if we can give some list of agents in G : i_0, i_1, \dots, i_n and some list of states u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n , such that

$s \sim_{i_0} u_1, u_1 \sim_{i_1} u_2, \dots, u_n \sim_{i_n} t. s \approx_G t$ would then mean that there is a `C_path` from s to t , where every agent in the given list of agents is also in G . We require that G is nonempty by requiring that our list of agents is also nonempty (line 3). This still allows us to prove $s \approx_G s$, through the reflexive path $s \sim_i s$ for any $i \in G$.

We use our defined `C_path` to define truth in a model in Lean as follows:

```

1 def s_entails_CLC {agents : Type} (m : modelECL agents) :
2   m.f.states → formCLC agents → Prop
3   ...
4   | s ('K i  $\varphi$ ) :=  $\forall$  t : m.f.states, t  $\in$  (m.f.rel i s) →
5     s_entails_CLC t  $\varphi$ 
6   | s ('C G  $\varphi$ ) :=  $\forall$  t : m.f.states, ( $\exists$  la, ( $\forall$  a  $\in$  la, a  $\in$  G)  $\wedge$ 
7      $\exists$  ls, C_path la ls s t) → s_entails_CLC t  $\varphi$ 

```

Here we omit the cases for operators that are also in CL, but the full definition can be found in the file `semantics/semanticsCLC.lean`.

We discuss one lemma about semantic entailment here, that relates to finite conjunctions: we prove that finite conjunction is true in a model iff all elements of the conjunction are true in that model. We prove this trivially by induction on the list of formulas in our conjunction:

```

1 lemma s_entails_CLC_conjunction {agents : Type}
2   {m : modelECL agents} {s : m.f.states}
3   { $\varphi$ s : list (formCLC agents)} :
4   s_entails_CLC m s (finite_conjunction  $\varphi$ s)  $\leftrightarrow$ 
5    $\forall$   $\varphi \in \varphi$ s, s_entails_CLC m s  $\varphi$  :=
6 begin
7   induction  $\varphi$ s with  $\varphi$   $\varphi$ s ih,
8   { simp [finite_conjunction],
9     show s_entails_CLC m s 'T,
10    simp [s_entails_CLC], },
11  { unfold finite_conjunction,
12    show s_entails_CLC m s ( $\varphi$  ' $\wedge$  finite_conjunction  $\varphi$ s)  $\leftrightarrow$  _,
13    simp [s_entails_CLC],
14    intro h,
15    exact ih, },
16 end

```

Validity in a model ($M \models \phi$), and global validity ($\models \phi$) are again defined as usual.

3.3 Axioms

For CLC, the axioms for CL are extended with the following axioms from epistemic logic:

(K) $\vdash K_i(\varphi \rightarrow \psi) \rightarrow (K_i\varphi \rightarrow K_i\psi)$
(T) $\vdash K_i\varphi \rightarrow \varphi$
(4) $\vdash K_i\varphi \rightarrow K_iK_i\varphi$
(5) $\vdash \neg K_i\varphi \rightarrow K_i\neg K_i\varphi$
(C) $\vdash C_G\varphi \rightarrow E_G(\varphi \wedge C_G\varphi)$
(RN) $\vdash \varphi \Rightarrow \vdash K_i\varphi$
(RC) $\vdash \psi \rightarrow E_G(\varphi \wedge \psi) \Rightarrow \vdash \psi \rightarrow C_G\varphi$

In Lean we again define this axiomatic system as an inductive predicate, as we did for CL. In the code below, we again exclude the cases that are the same as in `axCL` but the full definition can be found in the file `syntax/syntaxCLC.lean`. Note the need for the hypothesis `[hN : fintype agents]`, corresponding to the requirement that N is finite, due to how we defined the $E_G\varphi$ operator.

```

1 inductive axCLC {agents : Type} [hN : fintype agents] :
2   formCLC agents → Prop
3   ...
4   | K {ψ ψ} {i} :
5     axCLC (('K i (ψ '→ ψ)) '→ (('K i ψ) '→ ('K i ψ)))
6   | T {ψ} {i} : axCLC (('K i ψ) '→ ψ)
7   | Four {ψ} {i} : axCLC (('K i ψ) '→ ('K i ('K i ψ)))
8   | Five {ψ} {i} : axCLC (('¬ 'K i (ψ)) '→ (('K i ('¬ 'K i ψ))))
9   | C {ψ} {G} : axCLC (('C G ψ) '→ ('E G (ψ '∧ ('C G ψ))))
10  | RN {ψ} {i} (h: axCLC ψ) : axCLC ('K i ψ)
11  | RC {ψ ψ} {G} (h: axCLC (ψ '→ ('E G (ψ '∧ ψ)))) :
12    axCLC (ψ '→ ('C G ψ))
13
14 prefix `!` : 70 := axCLC

```

Given that this axiomatic system extends the CL axiomatic system, we can use it to instantiate our remaining formula Lean classes `Pformula_ax` and `Cformula`. We also choose to define new Lean classes for the epistemic operators and their related axioms. In this case we create one formula class for individual knowledge `Kformula`, and another for common knowledge `Cformula`:

```

1 -- Individual Knowledge
2 class Kformula (agents : out_param Type) (form : Type)
3   [pf : Pformula_ax form] :=
4   (knows : agents → form → form)
5   (K : ∀ ψ ψ i,
6     ! ((knows i (ψ → ψ)) → ((knows i ψ) → (knows i ψ))))
7   (T : ∀ ψ i, ! ((knows i ψ) → ψ))
8   (Four : ∀ ψ i, ! ((knows i ψ) → (knows i (knows i ψ))))
9   (Five : ∀ ψ i,
10    ! ((¬ (knows i (ψ))) → (knows i (¬ (knows i ψ)))))
11   (RN : ∀ ψ i, ! ψ → ! (knows i ψ))
12
13 notation `K` : 77 := Kformula.knows
14 notation `E` : 77 := λ G ψ, (finite_conjunction (list.map

```

```

15   (λ i, K' i φ) (finset.to_list (finite.to_finset
16   (finite.of_fintype G))))))
17
18   -- Common Knowledge
19   class Cformula (agents : out_param Type) [hN : fintype agents]
20     (form : Type) [pf : Pformula_ax form]
21     [kf : Kformula agents form] :=
22   (common_know : (set (agents)) → form → form)
23   (C : ∀ φ: form, ∀ G: set (agents),
24     ⊢' ((common_know G φ) →' (E' G (φ ∧' (common_know G φ))))))
25   (RC : ∀ φ ψ : form, ∀ G : set (agents),
26     ⊢' (ψ →' (E' G (φ ∧' ψ))) → ⊢' (ψ →' (common_know G φ)))
27
28   notation `C'` : 77 := Cformula.common_know

```

Note here that although we require a `Kformula` to have propositional operators and axioms, we do not require CL operators and axioms. A `Cformula` has two additional requirements. First, it specifies that N is finite, because the **(C)** and **(RC)** rules involve the $E_G\varphi$ operator. Secondly, a `Cformula` is required to have the operators and axioms related to individual knowledge.

Given these class definitions, we can instantiate these classes for our `formCLC` syntax by directly passing the already defined operators and axioms. All these class instances can be found in the file `syntax/syntaxCLC.lean`.

Soundness.

Theorem 3 (Soundness of CLC [1, Lemma 1]).

Proof. Trivially, we have $\vdash \varphi \Rightarrow \models \varphi$.

Despite this proof being simple, translating it into Lean is not entirely straightforward, so we go into more depth here. We prove this theorem by induction on the proof of $\vdash \varphi$, in the same way we proved that CL is sound in Theorem 1. As in Theorem 1, most of the new cases can be proven directly from the given assumptions. Cases **(T)**, **(4)** and **(5)**, additionally rely on the fact that epistemic relations are equivalence relations in their proofs. Cases **(C)** and **(RC)** are a little more complex, as they involve the $C_G\varphi$ operator. To reason about the truth of this operator we need to reason about the common knowledge relation \approx_G , and in Lean this takes the form of having to “build” a `C_path` between worlds.

We go into the case for axiom **(C)**, in more detail as an example, but the full proof can be found in the file `soundness/soundnessCLC.lean`. Given $M, s \models C_G\varphi$ we need to show $M, s \models E_G(\varphi \wedge C_G\varphi)$. First we use the lemma `s_entails_CLC_conjunction` to change the goal to $\forall i \in G, M, s \models K_i(\varphi \wedge C_G\varphi)$ (line 9). After some unfolding, this means that given some $i \in G$ and state t such that $s \sim_i t$ we need to show $M, t \models \varphi$ and $M, t \models C_G\varphi$. For the first case (lines 16-23), given $s \sim_i t$, we know there is a path $s \approx_G t$. We build this `C_path` in Lean with agent i (line 19) and an empty list of states (line

21). Given that $M, s \models_{C_G} \varphi$, we must then have $M, t \models \varphi$. For the second case (lines 24-33) we need to show that for every world u , such that $t \approx_G u$, we have $M, u \models \varphi$. Note that we must have $s \approx_G u$, given that we have $s \sim_i t$ and $t \approx_G u$. In Lean we can thus build a `C_path` with agent i followed by all the agents in the `C_path` from t to u represented by the variable `js` (line 29), and state t followed by all the states in the `C_path` from t to u represented by the variable `us` (line 31). Thus from $M, s \models_{C_G} \varphi$, we then know that $M, u \models \varphi$.

```

1  theorem soundnessCLC {agents: Type} [hN : fintype agents]
2    (ψ : formCLC agents) : '⊢ ψ → '⊨ ψ :=
3  begin
4    intro h,
5    induction ' h,
6    ...
7    -- C
8    { intros m s h,
9      rw s_entails_CLC_conjunction,
10     intros ψ hψ,
11     simp at hψ, cases hψ with i hi, cases hi with hi hψ,
12     rw [←(hψ)],
13     unfold s_entails_CLC,
14     intros t hts,
15     split,
16     { apply h,
17       split,
18       { split,
19         { show ∀ a, a ∈ [i] → a ∈ G,
20           simp, exact hi, },
21         { apply exists.intro [],
22           unfold C_path,
23           exact hts, }, }, },
24     { intros u hu, cases hu with js hu,
25       cases hu with hjs hu, cases hu with us htU,
26       apply h,
27       split,
28       { split,
29         { show ∀ a, a ∈ (i :: js) → a ∈ G,
30           simp, exact and.intro hi hjs, },
31         { apply exists.intro (t :: us),
32           unfold C_path,
33           exact and.intro hts htU, }, }, }, },
34     ...
35  end

```

3.4 Completeness

Canonical Model Construction. We show completeness of CLC by canonical model construction. As already mentioned, we will prove that our canonical

model includes a truly playable effectivity structure, by building a finite model (with finite states). We will, therefore, not be able to build our canonical model as we did for CL, where S^C was defined as the set of all maximal CL-consistent sets of formulas. Instead we follow a new approach: rather than creating a single canonical model within which each consistent formula is true at some world, we will create a finite model for each such formula, where that formula is true at some world. We will do this by starting with a single canonical coalition model for CLC, exactly as we did for CL. For each formula, we then filter this model into a finite model, and add knowledge relations to transform it into an epistemic coalition model.

As mentioned, we start by building a canonical coalition model. We define $M^{C'} := (F^{C'}, V^{C'})$, where $F^{C'} := (S^{C'}, E^{C'})$:

$S^{C'}$ is the set of all maximal CLC-consistent set of formulas

$E^{C'}$ is the playable effectivity structure :

$$\begin{aligned} X \in E^{C'}(s)(N) &\text{ iff } \forall \varphi, \tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X^c \rightarrow [\emptyset]\varphi \notin s, \text{ where } \tilde{\varphi} := \{t \in S^{C'} \mid \varphi \in t\} \\ X \in E^{C'}(s)(G) &\text{ iff } \exists \varphi, \tilde{\varphi} \subseteq X \wedge [G]\varphi \in s, \text{ when } G \neq N \end{aligned}$$

$V^{C'}$ is the usual valuation function : $s \in V^{C'}(p)$ iff $p \in s$.

These definitions for $S^{C'}$, $E^{C'}$ and $V^{C'}$ are analogous to those of the CL canonical model, thus $E^{C'}$ is playable by the same proof as when building the canonical model for CL. In Lean, this means we can completely reuse our canonical model (that contains a proof for playability), as it was defined for any extension of CL, by using the generic `class CLformula` and `class Pformula_ax`.

Next, given some φ , we filter $S^{C'}$ into a finite set of states S^f . We achieve this by creating a finite closure $cl(\varphi)$, defined as the smallest set such that:

- For any $\psi \in cl(\varphi)$ all subformulas of ψ are also contained in $cl(\varphi)$.
- For any $\psi \in cl(\varphi)$, if ψ is not of the form $\neg\chi$, then $\neg\chi \in cl(\varphi)$
 $cl(\varphi)$ is thus closed under single negations
- If $C_G\varphi \in cl(\varphi)$, then for all $i \in G$, $K_i C_G\varphi \in cl(\varphi)$
- If $[G]\varphi \in cl(\varphi)$, then $C_G[G]\varphi \in cl(\varphi)$

Note that we adjust the definition for this closure slightly from to the work by Ågotnes and Alechina [1], as we allow the formula $C_\emptyset\varphi$, and thus do not need to consider the case $G = \emptyset$ separately. Additionally, we change the first requirement to hold for all formulas in the closure, rather than only requiring $cl(\varphi)$ to contain the subformulas of φ . This change will help us prove the truth lemma, where we will perform induction on an arbitrary $\psi \in cl(\varphi)$. We note that for Ågotnes and Alechina [1] these two requirements are equivalent due to their syntax being defined from different base operators than ours (i.e. by a different grammar).

The set $cl(\varphi)$ can be built inductively on the length of φ :

Case $cl(\perp)$	$:= \{\perp, \top\}$
Case $cl(p)$	$:= \{p, \neg p, \perp, \top\}$
Case $cl(\psi \wedge \chi)$	$:= cl(\psi) \cup cl(\chi) \cup \{\psi \wedge \chi, \neg(\psi \wedge \chi)\}$
Case $cl(\psi \rightarrow \perp)$	$:= cl(\psi) \cup cl(\perp) \cup \{\psi \rightarrow \perp\}$
Case $cl(\psi \rightarrow \chi), \chi \neq \perp$	$:= cl(\psi) \cup cl(\chi) \cup \{\psi \rightarrow \chi, \neg(\psi \rightarrow \chi)\}$
Case $cl([G]\psi)$	$:= cl(\psi) \cup \{[G]\psi, \neg([G]\psi), C_G[G]\psi, \neg(C_G[G]\psi)\} \cup$ $\{K_i C_G[G]\psi : i \in G\} \cup \{\neg(K_i C_G[G]\psi) : i \in G\}$
Case $cl(K_i \psi)$	$:= cl(\psi) \cup \{K_i \psi, \neg(K_i \psi)\}$
Case $cl(C_G \psi)$	$:= cl(\psi) \cup \{C_G \psi, \neg(C_G \psi)\} \cup$ $\{K_i C_G \psi : i \in G\} \cup \{\neg(K_i C_G \psi) : i \in G\}$

Note that sets like $\{K_i C_G[G]\psi : i \in G\}$ or $\{\neg(K_i C_G \psi) : i \in G\}$ must be finite, because G is. Thus each atomic proposition and operator in φ adds a finite number of formulas to $cl(\varphi)$. Given a finite φ , the resulting set $cl(\varphi)$ must therefore be finite.

In Lean we build our closure inductively, exactly as above:

```

1 noncomputable def cl_C {agents : Type} [hN : fintype agents]
2   (G : set (agents)) (ϕ : formCLC agents) :
3   finset (formCLC agents) :=
4   finset.image (λ i, 'K (i) ('C G ϕ)) (to_finset G) ∪
5   finset.image (λ i, ('¬ 'K (i) ('C G ϕ))) (to_finset G)
6
7 noncomputable def cl {agents : Type} [hN : fintype agents] :
8   formCLC agents → finset (formCLC agents)
9 | '⊥      := {'⊥, '¬ '⊥}
10 | (var n) := {var n, '¬ var n, '⊥, '¬ '⊥}
11 | (ϕ '→ ψ) := cl ϕ ∪ cl ψ ∪ (ite (ψ = '⊥) {(imp ϕ '⊥)}
12   {(imp ϕ ψ), '¬ (imp ϕ ψ)})
13 | (ϕ '∧ ψ) := cl ϕ ∪ cl ψ ∪ {(and ϕ ψ), '¬ (and ϕ ψ)}
14 | ('[G] ϕ) := cl ϕ ∪ {'[G] ϕ, '¬ '[G] ϕ} ∪
15   {'C (G) ('[G] ϕ), '¬ ('C (G) ('[G] ϕ))} ∪
16   cl_C G ('[G] ϕ)
17 | ('K i ϕ) := cl ϕ ∪ {'K i ϕ, '¬ ('K i ϕ)}
18 | ('C G ϕ) := cl ϕ ∪ {'C G ϕ, '¬ ('C G ϕ)} ∪ cl_C G ϕ
    
```

Here we first define the sets $\{K_i C_G \psi : i \in G\} \cup \{\neg(K_i C_G \psi) : i \in G\}$ on their own as `cl_C` (lines 1-5). We ensure that the result of this function is finite, by using the Lean datatype `finset`. We create this resulting `finset`, by first casting G itself from a normal Lean `set` to a `finset` (lines 4 & 5). Lean knows this is possible, because N is finite, as indicated by the hypothesis `[hN : fintype agents]` (line 1). Then we can simply image G as described. We then define the closure inductively on the size of φ exactly as we would on paper (lines 7-18).

In Lean we also choose to prove several Lemmas about this closure that would be trivial in a paper proof. The full proofs for these lemmas can be found in the file `completeness/closureCLC.lean`. We prove that $cl(\varphi)$ contains φ (lines 1-2), and that if $cl(\varphi)$ contains $C_G \psi$, then it must also contain $K_i C_G \psi$, for every

$i \in G$ (lines 4-7). Lastly we prove that the closure is indeed closed under single negations (lines 9-11).

```

1 lemma cl_contains_phi {agents : Type} [hN : fintype agents]
2   (ψ : formCLC agents) : ψ ∈ cl ψ := ...
3
4 lemma cl_C_contains_KC {agents : Type} [hN : fintype agents]
5   {ψ ψ : formCLC agents} {G : set agents}
6   {i : agents} (hi : i ∈ G) (h : 'C G ψ ∈ cl ψ) :
7   'K i ('C G ψ) ∈ cl ψ := ...
8
9 lemma cl_closed_single_neg {agents : Type} [hN : fintype agents]
10  (ψ x : formCLC agents) (hx : x ∈ cl ψ) :
11  ∃ ψ, (ψ ∈ cl ψ ∧ '⊢ (ψ '↔ ('¬ x))) := ...

```

Next we look at how sub-formulas behave in our closure. This first requires defining sub-formulas, which we do as an inductive proposition (lines 1-12). We build cases for each of our operators (lines 6-12), where for instance φ would be a sub-formula of $\varphi \wedge \psi$ (line 6). Additionally, we add the requirements that our sub-formula definition must be reflexive and transitive (lines 3 - 5). We then can prove that if φ is a sub-formula of ψ , then $cl(\varphi) \subseteq cl(\psi)$, as $cl(\psi)$ always includes $cl(\varphi)$ by definition. We use this lemma to prove that $cl(\psi)$ contains all sub-formulas of ψ (lines 19-22). The last lemma we need to prove in Lean about subformulas is the first requirement for the closure: that for any $\psi \in cl(\varphi)$ all subformulas of ψ are also contained in $cl(\varphi)$ (lines 24-27). This proof is again trivial on paper and just requires going through all the cases. The full proofs for all the lemmas about subformulas can be found in the file `completeness/closureCLC.lean`.

```

1 inductive subformula {agents : Type} :
2   formCLC agents → formCLC agents → Prop
3 | refl      {ψ}      : subformula ψ ψ
4 | trans    {ψ ψ χ}  : subformula ψ ψ → subformula ψ χ →
5   subformula ψ χ
6 | and_left {ψ ψ}    : subformula ψ (ψ '∧ ψ)
7 | and_right {ψ ψ}   : subformula ψ (ψ '∧ ψ)
8 | imp_left  {ψ ψ}   : subformula ψ (ψ '→ ψ)
9 | imp_right {ψ ψ}   : subformula ψ (ψ '→ ψ)
10 | effectivity {G} {ψ} : subformula ψ ('[G] ψ)
11 | knows      {i} {ψ} : subformula ψ ('K i ψ)
12 | common_know {G} {ψ} : subformula ψ ('C G ψ)
13
14 lemma subformula.cl_subset {agents : Type}
15   [ha : nonempty agents] [hN : fintype agents]
16   {ψ ψ : formCLC agents} (h : subformula ψ ψ) :
17   cl ψ ⊆ cl ψ := ...
18
19 lemma subformula.mem_cl {agents : Type}
20   [ha : nonempty agents] [hN : fintype agents]
21   {ψ ψ : formCLC agents} (h : subformula ψ ψ) : ψ ∈ cl ψ :=
22   h.cl_subset (cl_contains_phi ψ)

```

```

23
24 lemma subformula.in_cl_sub {agents : Type} [hN : fintype agents]
25   {ψ ψ χ : formCLC agents}
26   (hcl : ψ ∈ cl ψ) (hsub : subformula χ ψ) :
27   χ ∈ cl ψ := ...
    
```

Given some φ , we can now filter $M^{C'}$ through $cl(\varphi)$, to construct a finite model $M^f := (F^f, V^f)$, where $F^f := (S^f, E^f, \{\sim_i^f : i \in N\})$. We construct M^f as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S^f &:= \{(s^f) \mid s \in S^{C'}\}, & \text{where } s^f &:= (s \cap cl(\varphi)) \\
 E^f &:= X \in E^f(s)(N) & \text{iff } \exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \text{ and } \widetilde{\phi}_X \in E^{C'}(t)(N) \\
 &X \in E^f(s)(G \subset N) & \text{iff } \forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_X \in E^{C'}(t)(G) \\
 \sim_i^f &:= (s^f) \sim_i^f (t^f) & \text{iff } \{\varphi \mid K_i \varphi \in s^f\} = \{\varphi \mid K_i \varphi \in t^f\} \\
 V^f &:= s \in V(p) & \text{iff } p \in s
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $\phi_X := \bigvee_{s^f \in X} \phi^{s^f}$ is the disjunction of a set of filtered states, $\phi^{s^f} := \bigwedge_{\psi \in s^f} \psi$ is the conjunction of the formulas in a filtered state, and $\widetilde{\psi} := \{t \in S^{C'} \mid \psi \in t\}$ is defined as before. Note that S^f is finite because $cl(\varphi)$ is, and that \sim_i^f is an equivalence relation by definition.

These definitions can be translated pretty directly into Lean, although it might not look so direct, due to having to distinguish between a set and a finite set in Lean. Thus, to define S^f in Lean, we start with $cl(\varphi)$, as we have already defined this as a `finset`. We take the powerset of $cl(\varphi)$ (line 7), which Lean knows must also be finite. This finite powerset is then filtered (line 4) to include only those elements s^f , for which there exists some $s \in S^{C'}$ (line 5) such that $s^f = s \cap cl(\varphi)$ (line 6). In order to compare these, given that s^f and $cl(\varphi)$ are both a `finset`, but s is a Lean `set`, we convert both to sets first (line 6).

```

1 def S_f {agents form : Type} (m : modelCL agents)
2   [hm : set_like m.f.states form]
3   (cl : form → finset (form)) (ψ : form) : Type :=
4   finset.attach (finset.filter
5     (λ sf, ∃ s : m.f.states,
6       {x | x ∈ cl(ψ) ∧ x ∈ s} = {x | x ∈ sf}))
7   (finset.powerset (cl(ψ)))
    
```

Note that we keep the definition for S^f to any model (line 1), so long as the states are a set of formulas (line 2). Doing so allows us keep our definition simpler, by not requiring all the hypothesis needed to create our canonical model (for instance that N is nonempty, and $\not\vdash \perp$). When we need additional hypothesis about our model, for instance that sets are maximally consistent, we can just specify that our model is indeed the previously defined canonical coalition model $M^{C'}$. For S^f , however, there are many other definitions that relate only to S^f (ignoring properties of $M^{C'}$), for instance the definitions for ϕ_X and ϕ^{s^f} :

```

1 noncomputable def phi_s_f {agents form : Type}
2   [pf : Pformula form]
3   {m : modelCL agents} [hm : set_like m.f.states form]
    
```

```

4   {cl : form → finset (form)} {ψ : form} (sf : S_f m cl ψ) :
5   form :=
6   finite_conjunction (finset.to_list (sf.1))
7
8   noncomputable def phi_X_list ... :
9     list (S_f m cl ψ) → list (form)
10  | list.nil      := list.nil
11  | (sf :: ss)   := ((phi_s_f sf) :: phi_X_list ss)
12
13  noncomputable def phi_X_finset ...
14    (X : finset (S_f m cl ψ)) : form :=
15    finite_disjunction (phi_X_list (finset.to_list X))
16
17  noncomputable def phi_X_set ...
18    (X : set (S_f m cl ψ)) : form :=
19    phi_X_finset (finite.to_finset (finite.of_fintype X))

```

Here we only include the full set of hypotheses for `phi_s_f`, however the other definitions include all the the same hypotheses. Defining ϕ^{s^f} in Lean (lines 1-6) is as simple as converting our finite set to a list and then creating a conjunction from that list (line 6). We then define ϕ_X in several steps. First we define a function `phi_X_list` (lines 8-11) to map X to $\{\phi^{s^f} : s^f \in X\}$. Next, we define ϕ_X for finite sets (lines 13-15), as we can convert that finite set to a list, map it to formulas with `phi_X_list`, and then return the disjunction of that mapped list. Lastly, for the `set` datatype, we define ϕ_X (lines 17-19) by converting to a `finset`, which we can do because we know a set of some finite Type must be finite. Splitting this definition up into three parts may seem to add complexity, however it makes it easier to define lemmas about each “stage”, with separate data types. In Lean, separating proofs in this way often makes them simpler, as we break them down into smaller steps. We can prove lemmas more easily for a list, which is ordered, finite, and allows induction. Then, it is easy to show that if some lemma holds for a list, it must work for a list created from a (finite) set. Attempting to do this all at once would require keeping track of all the conversions throughout one proof and how they relate to one another, and this is non-trivial in Lean, especially with inductive proofs. Thus, we have many lemmas about each “step” of our ϕ_X definition, many of which have a “version” for each datatype (i.e. proving something for ϕ_X given a Lean `set`, `finset` and `list`). These lemmas can be found in the file `completeness/canonical_filtering.lean`.

Next, we use our definition(s) for ϕ_X to define E^f , and then our whole model M^f . Note that we define E^f (lines 1-19) and M^f (lines 21-42), specifically given our already defined canonical model $M^{C'}$ (not for a generic model). This choice is made because we need properties of $M^{C'}$ to prove true playability of E^f , and thus to define M^f . The proofs for playability will be elaborated on later, but for now we note that we build our truly playable effectivity structure, with `truly_playable_from_finite` (line 30) from a playable effectivity structure,

given that S^f is finite. \sim_i^f is defined in lines 37 - 38, exactly as in the paper proof. We also trivially prove that the epistemic accessibility relations are equivalence relations in lines 39-41. Lastly, V^f is defined as before in line 42.

```

1  def E_f {agents form : Type} [ha : nonempty agents]
2    [pf : Pformula_ax form] [clf : CLformula agents form]
3    {hnpr : ¬ ⊢' (⊥' : form)} {cl : form → finset (form)}
4    {ψ : form} :
5    (S_f (canonical_model_CL agents form hnpr) cl ψ) →
6      (set agents) →
7      (set (set (S_f (canonical_model_CL agents form hnpr) cl ψ)))
8      :=
9    λ sf G, {X | ite (G = univ)
10      -- condition G = N
11      (∃ t, sf = (s_f cl ψ t) ∧
12        (tilde (canonical_model_CL agents form hnpr).f.states
13          (phi_X_set X)) ∈
14          (canonical_model_CL agents form hnpr).f.E.E (t) (G))
15      -- condition G ≠ N
16      (∀ t, sf = (s_f cl ψ t) →
17        (tilde (canonical_model_CL agents form hnpr).f.states
18          (phi_X_set X)) ∈
19          (canonical_model_CL agents form hnpr).f.E.E (t) (G))}
20
21  noncomputable def filtered_model_CLC
22    {agents form : Type} [ha : nonempty agents]
23    [pf : Pformula_ax form] [clf : CLformula agents form]
24    [kf : Kformula agents form] {hnpr : ¬ ⊢' (⊥' : form)}
25    {cl : form → finset (form)} {ψ : form} :
26    modelECL agents :=
27    { f :=
28      { states := S_f (canonical_model_CL agents form hnpr) cl ψ,
29        hs := canonical.S_f.nonempty _ _ _,
30        E := truly_playable_from_finite
31          { E := E_f,
32            liveness := Ef_liveness,
33            safety := Ef_safety,
34            N_max := Ef_nmax,
35            mono := Ef_mono,
36            superadd := Ef_superadd, },
37        rel := λ i s, {t | {ψ | K' (i) (ψ) ∈ s} =
38          {ψ | K' (i) (ψ) ∈ t}},
39        rfl := λ i s, rfl,
40        sym := λ i s t ht, eq.symm ht,
41        trans := λ i s t u hst ht, eq.trans hst ht, },
42    v := λ n, {s | (Pformula.var n) ∈ s.1.1}, }

```

Lemmas about the Filtered Canonical Model. We note four useful properties about S^f , that will be used to prove playability of E^f and completeness

of CLC. Lemma 6 and Lemma 7 are part of the Truth Lemma for CLC which we will prove later (Lemma 8). We will only refer to the Lean translations when they differ interestingly from the paper proof. The full Lean versions can be found in the file `completeness/canonical_filtering.lean`.

Lemma 4. $\vdash \phi_{S^f}$

Proof. 1. Assume towards a contradiction that $\not\vdash \phi_{S^f}$

2. Consider some $t \in S^{C'}$ such that $\neg\phi_{S^f} \in t$, which must exist because $\neg\phi_{S^f}$ is consistent, from 1.
3. $\vdash \phi^{t^f} \rightarrow \phi_{S^f}$, by propositional logic.
4. $\phi^{t^f} \in t$, by propositional logic, because $t^f \subseteq t$.
5. $\phi_{S^f} \in t$, by propositional logic, from 3 & 4.
6. Contradiction from 2 and 5.

Lemma 5. $\forall s, t \in S^{C'}, s^f \neq t^f \Rightarrow \vdash \phi^{s^f} \rightarrow \neg\phi^{t^f}$

Proof. 1. Assume towards a contradiction $\not\vdash \phi^{s^f} \rightarrow \neg\phi^{t^f}$

2. Consider some $u \in S^{C'}$ such that $\neg(\phi^{s^f} \rightarrow \neg\phi^{t^f}) \in u$, which must exist because $\neg(\phi^{s^f} \rightarrow \neg\phi^{t^f})$ is consistent, from 1.
3. $\phi^{s^f} \wedge \phi^{t^f} \in u$, by propositional logic, from 2.
4. Consider some $\psi \in s^f \cup t^f$ such that $\psi \notin s^f \vee \psi \notin t^f$, which must exist because $s^f \neq t^f$. Let v^f be either s^f or t^f , such that $\psi \notin v^f$
5. $\psi \notin v$, from 4, by definition of S^f , because $\psi \in cl(\varphi)$.
6. $\neg\psi \in v$, from 5, because v is maximally consistent.
7. Consider some χ such that $(\vdash \chi \leftrightarrow \neg\psi) \wedge (\chi \in cl(\varphi))$, which must exist because cl is closed under single negations.
8. $\chi \in v$, from 6 & 7, because v is maximally consistent.
9. $\chi \in v^f$, from 7 & 8, by definition of S^f .
10. $\{\psi, \chi\} \subseteq s^f \cup t^f$, from 4 & 9.
11. $\vdash \phi^{s^f} \wedge \phi^{t^f} \rightarrow \perp$, by propositional logic, from 7 & 10.
12. $\perp \in u$, by propositional logic, from 3 & 11, which contradicts the consistency of u .

Lemma 6 ([1, Lemma 2.1]). $\forall \psi \in cl(\varphi), \vdash \phi_{\{s^f | \psi \in s^f\}} \leftrightarrow \psi$

Proof. Let ψ be some $\psi \in cl(\varphi)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \phi_{\{s^f | \psi \in s^f\}} \\
\leftrightarrow & \bigvee_{\{s^f | \psi \in s^f\}} \phi^{s^f}, \text{ by definition of } \phi_X. \\
\leftrightarrow & \bigvee_{\{s^f | \psi \in s^f\}} (\psi \wedge \phi^{s^f}), \text{ by propositional logic.} \\
\leftrightarrow & \perp \vee (\bigvee_{\{s^f | \psi \in s^f\}} (\psi \wedge \phi^{s^f})), \text{ by propositional logic.} \\
\leftrightarrow & (\bigvee_{\{t^f | \neg\psi \in t^f\}} (\psi \wedge \phi^{t^f})) \vee (\bigvee_{\{s^f | \psi \in s^f\}} (\psi \wedge \phi^{s^f})), \text{ by propositional logic.} \\
\leftrightarrow & \psi \wedge ((\bigvee_{\{t^f | \neg\psi \in t^f\}} \phi^{t^f}) \vee (\bigvee_{\{s^f | \psi \in s^f\}} \phi^{s^f})), \text{ by propositional logic.} \\
\leftrightarrow & \psi \wedge (\bigvee_{\{s^f \in S^f\}} \phi^{s^f}), \text{ because } \{t^f | \neg\psi \in t^f\} \cup \{s^f | \psi \in s^f\} = S^f.
\end{aligned}$$

$\leftrightarrow \psi \wedge \top$, from Lemma 4.
 $\leftrightarrow \psi$, by propositional logic.

We note that in Lean the propositional steps are proved given a Lean `list`, for simplicity (lines 1 - 7). The relevant part of Lemma 4, is passed as hypothesis `hSf` in lines 5-6. If this Lemma holds for a `list`, it must hold for a `finset` converted into a `list` (lines 10-14), and thus for a `set`, converted into `finset` (lines 16-34). In the latter, we prove the mentioned relevant part of Lemma 4: $\vdash (\bigvee_{\{tf \mid \neg \psi \in tf\}} \phi^{tf}) \vee (\bigvee_{\{sf \mid \psi \in sf\}} \phi^{sf})$ to pass forward (lines 25-33). Note that Lemma 4 is named `univ_disjunct_provability` in Lean. We do not provide all hypotheses for every Lean `lemma` here for readability.

```

1 lemma phi_X_contains_iff_psi_list {agents form : Type} ...
2   {sfs tfs : list (S_f (canonical_model_CL _ _ hnpr) cl ψ)}
3   (hsfs : ∀ sf, sf ∈ sfs → ψ ∈ sf)
4   (htfs : ∀ tf, tf ∈ tfs → ψ ∉ tf)
5   (hSf : ⊢' (finite_disjunction (phi_X_list tfs)) ∨'
6     (finite_disjunction (phi_X_list sfs))) :
7   ⊢' ((finite_disjunction (phi_X_list sfs)) ↔' ψ) := ...
8
9 lemma phi_X_contains_iff_psi_finset {agents form : Type} ...
10  {sfs : finset (S_f (canonical_model_CL _ _ hnpr) cl ψ)}
11  (hsfs : ∀ sf, sf ∈ sfs → ψ ∈ sf)
12  (htfs : ∀ tf, tf ∉ sfs → ψ ∉ tf)
13  (hSf : ⊢' ((phi_X_finset sfsc) ∨' (phi_X_finset sfs))) :
14  ⊢' ( (phi_X_finset sfs) ↔' ψ) := ...
15
16 lemma phi_X_contains_iff_psi {agents form : Type} ...
17   (hψ : ψ ∈ cl ψ) :
18   ⊢' (phi_X_set {sf : ... | ψ ∈ sf} ↔' ψ) :=
19 begin
20   apply phi_X_contains_iff_psi_finset hcl hψ,
21   -- ∀ sf, sf ∈ phi {sf | ψ ∈ sf} → ψ ∈ sf
22   simp,
23   -- ∀ tf, tf ∉ phi {sf | ψ ∈ sf} → ψ ∉ sf
24   simp,
25   -- ⊢ (phi sfsc) ∨ (phi sfs) ↔ ⊢ phi (sfsc ∪ sfs)
26   apply (phi_X_finset_disjunct_of_disjuncts _ _).mpr,
27   -- ⊢ phi Sf → phi sfsc ∪ sfs and we have ⊢ phi Sf
28   apply MP' (univ_disjunct_provability hnpr cl ψ),
29   -- Sf ⊆ sfsc ∪ sfs ⇒ ⊢ phi Sf → phi sfsc ∪ sfs
30   apply phi_X_subset_Y_imp,
31   -- Sf ⊆ sfsc ∪ sfs
32   intros sf hsf, simp at *,
33   rw or.comm, exact (em (ψ ∈ sf)),
34 end

```

Lemma 7 ([1, Lemma 2.2]). $\tilde{\psi} \in E^{C'}(s)(G)$ iff $[G]\psi \in s$

Proof. We consider the case when $G = N$ and $G \neq N$ separately.

1. case $G = N$
 - 1.1. \Rightarrow
 - 1.1.1. Assume $\tilde{\psi} \in E^{C'}(s)(N)$.
 - 1.1.2. $\forall \chi, \tilde{\chi} \subseteq (\tilde{\psi})^c \rightarrow [\emptyset]\chi \notin s$, from 1.1.1, by definition of $E^{C'}$.
 - 1.1.3. $\forall \chi, \tilde{\chi} \subseteq \neg\psi \rightarrow [\emptyset]\chi \notin s$, from 1.1.2, because $(\tilde{\psi})^c = \neg\tilde{\psi}$.
 - 1.1.4. $[N]\psi \in s$, from 1.1.3, by axiom **(N)**.
 - 1.2. \Leftarrow
 - 1.2.1. Assume $[N]\psi \in s$.
 - 1.2.2. $\neg[\emptyset]\neg\psi \in s$, from 1.2.1
 - 1.2.3. $\neg\exists \chi, \tilde{\chi} \subseteq \neg\tilde{\psi} : [\emptyset]\chi \in s$, from proof by contradiction, else by the derived monotonicity axiom we would have $[\emptyset]\neg\psi \in s$, which contradicts with 1.2.2.
 - 1.2.4. $\forall \chi, \tilde{\chi} \subseteq \neg\tilde{\psi} : [\emptyset]\chi \notin s$, from 1.2.3, by first order logic.
 - 1.2.5. $\forall \chi, \tilde{\chi} \subseteq (\tilde{\psi})^c : [\emptyset]\chi \notin s$, because all $s \in S^{C'}$ are maximally consistent.
 - 1.2.6. $\tilde{\psi} \in E^{C'}(s)(N)$, from 1.2.5, by definition of $E^{C'}$.
2. case $G \neq N$
 - 2.1. \Rightarrow
 - 2.1.1. Assume $\tilde{\psi} \in E^{C'}(s)(G)$.
 - 2.1.2. Consider some χ such that $\tilde{\chi} \subseteq \tilde{\psi}$ and $[G]\chi \in s$, which exists by 2.1.1 and definition of $E^{C'}$.
 - 2.1.3. $\vdash \chi \rightarrow \psi$, from 2.1.2.
 - 2.1.4. $[G]\psi \in s$, from 2.1.2 & 2.1.3, by lemma 2.
 - 2.2. \Leftarrow is immediate by definition.

Playability of the Filtered Canonical Model. We prove that M^f meets the requirements for being a CLC model, by showing that, $E^f(s^f)$ is playable, for an arbitrary world s^f in the filtered model [1, Proposition 1]. Here again, we will only refer to the Lean version of this proof at points where it differs interestingly from the paper proof, but the full version can be found in the file `completeness/canonical_filtering.lean`.

1. $E^f(s^f)$ is live: $\forall G \subseteq N : \emptyset \notin E^f(s^f)(G)$
 - 1.1. First we note that $\tilde{\phi}_\emptyset = \tilde{\perp} = \emptyset$.
 - 1.1.1. $\phi_\emptyset = \perp$, because ϕ_\emptyset is an empty disjunction, thus $\tilde{\phi}_\emptyset = \tilde{\perp}$.
 - 1.1.2. $\perp = \emptyset$, because all $s \in S^{C'}$ are consistent.
 - 1.2. Assume towards a contradiction $\emptyset \in E^f(s^f)(G)$.
 - 1.3. Case: $G = N$
 - 1.3.1. Consider some $t \in S^{C'}$ such that $s^f = t^f$ and $\tilde{\phi}_\emptyset \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, which exists by 1.2 and definition of E^f .
 - 1.3.2. $\emptyset \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, from 1.3.1 & 1.1.
 - 1.3.3. $\emptyset \notin E(t)(N)$ because $E^{C'}(t)$ is live.
 - 1.3.4. Contradiction from 1.3.2 & 1.3.3.
 - 1.4. Case: $G \neq N$
 - 1.4.1. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow \tilde{\phi}_\emptyset \in E^{C'}(t)(G)$, from 1.2, by definition of E^f
 - 1.4.2. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow \emptyset \in E^{C'}(t)(G)$, from 1.4.1 & 1.1

- 1.4.3. $\emptyset \in E^{C'}(s)(G)$, from 1.4.2, when $s = t$.
- 1.4.4. $\emptyset \notin E^{C'}(s)(G)$ because $E^{C'}(s)$ is live.
- 1.4.5. Contradiction from 1.4.3 & 1.4.4.
2. $E^f(s^f)$ is safe: $\forall G \subseteq N : S^f \in E^f(s^f)(G)$
- 2.1. First we note that $\widetilde{\phi}_{S^f} = \widetilde{\top} = S^{C'}$, from Lemma 4.
- 2.2. Case: $G = N$
- 2.2.1. $S^f \in E^f(s^f)(N)$ iff $\exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f$ and $\widetilde{\phi}_{S^f} \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, by definition of E^f .
- 2.2.2. $S^f \in E^f(s^f)(N)$ iff $\exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f$ and $S^{C'} \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, from 2.1 & 2.2.1.
- 2.2.3. $\exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f$ and $S^{C'} \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, when $t = s$, because $S^{C'} \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, because $E^{C'}$ is safe.
- 2.2.4. $S^f \in E^f(s^f)(N)$, from 2.2.2 & 2.2.3.
- 2.3. Case: $G \neq N$
- 2.3.1. $S^f \in E^f(s^f)(G)$ iff $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_{S^f} \in E^{C'}(t)(G)$, by definition of E^f .
- 2.3.2. $S^f \in E^f(s^f)(G)$ iff $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow S^{C'} \in E^{C'}(t)(G)$, from 2.1 & 2.3.1.
- 2.3.3. $S^f \in E^f(s^f)(G)$, from 2.3.2, because $E^{C'}(t)$ is safe: $S^{C'} \in E^{C'}(t)(G)$.
3. $E^f(s^f)$ is N-maximal: $\forall X \subseteq S^f : X^c \notin E^f(s^f)(\emptyset) \Rightarrow X \in E^f(s^f)(N)$
- 3.1. Let $X \subseteq S^f$ be some set such that $X^c \notin E^f(s^f)\emptyset$.
- 3.2. $\neg(X^c \in E^f(s^f)(\emptyset))$, from 3.1.
- 3.3. $\neg(\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_{X^c} \in E^{C'}(t)(\emptyset))$, from 3.2, by definition of E^f .
- 3.4. $\exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f$ and $\widetilde{\phi}_{X^c} \notin E^{C'}(t)(\emptyset)$, from 3.3, by first order logic.
- 3.5. $\vdash \phi_{X^c} \leftrightarrow \neg\phi_X$, from Lemma 4 & Lemma 5.
- 3.6. $\exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f$ and $\neg\widetilde{\phi}_X \notin E^{C'}(t)(\emptyset)$, from 3.4 & 3.5.
- 3.7. $\exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f$ and $(\widetilde{\phi}_X)^c \notin E^{C'}(t)(\emptyset)$, from 3.6, because all $s \in S^{C'}$ are maximally consistent.
- 3.8. $\exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f$, and $\widetilde{\phi}_X \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, when $s = t$ from 3.7, because $E^{C'}(t)$ is N-maximal: $(\widetilde{\phi}_X)^c \notin E^{C'}(t)(\emptyset) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_X \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$
- 3.9. $E^f(s^f)(N)$, from 3.8, by definition of E^f .
4. $E^f(s^f)$ is outcome monotonic: $\forall G \subseteq N, \forall X \subseteq Y \subseteq S^f : X \in E^f(s^f)(G) \Rightarrow Y \in E^f(s^f)(G)$
- 4.1. Let G be some $G \subseteq N$ and X and Y be some $X \subseteq Y \subseteq S^f$. Assume $X \in E^f(s^f)(G)$.
- 4.2. First we show that $\forall t \in S^{C'}, \forall G \subseteq N$,
- $\widetilde{\phi}_X \in E^{C'}(t)(G) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_Y \in E^{C'}(t)(G)$
- 4.2.1. $\vdash \phi_X \rightarrow \phi_Y$, from 4.1 ($X \subseteq Y$).
- 4.2.2. $\widetilde{\phi}_X \subseteq \widetilde{\phi}_Y$, from 4.3.1, because all $s \in S^{C'}$ are maximally consistent.
- 4.2.3. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, \forall G \subseteq N, \widetilde{\phi}_X \in E^{C'}(t)(G) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_Y \in E^{C'}(t)(G)$, from 4.2.2, because $E^{C'}(t)$ is outcome monotonic.
- 4.3. Case $G = N$
- 4.3.1. $\exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f$ and $\widetilde{\phi}_X \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, from 4.1, by definition of E^f .
- 4.3.2. $\exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f$ and $\widetilde{\phi}_Y \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, from 4.2 & 4.3.1.

- 4.3.3. $Y \in E^f(s^f)(N)$, from 4.2.2, by definition of E^f .
- 4.4. Case: $G \neq N$
- 4.4.1. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_X \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, from 4.1, by definition of E^f .
- 4.4.2. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_Y \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, from 4.2 & 4.4.1.
- 4.4.3. $Y \in E^f(s^f)(G)$, from 4.4.2, by definition of E^f .
5. $E^f(s^f)$ is superadditive $\forall G, F \subseteq N$ (where $G \cap F = \emptyset$), $\forall X, Y \subseteq S^f : X \in E^f(s^f)(G)$ and $Y \in E^f(s^f)(F) \Rightarrow X \cap Y \in E^f(s^f)(G \cup F)$
- 5.1. Let $G, F \subseteq N$ be some groups of agents, such that $G \cap F = \emptyset$. Let $X, Y \subseteq S^{C'}$ be some sets such that $X \in E^f(s^f)(G)$ and $Y \in E^f(s^f)(F)$.
- 5.2. First we show that $\forall t \in S^{C'}, \forall G, F \subseteq N$, such that $G \cap F = \emptyset$, $\widetilde{\phi}_X \in E^{C'}(t)(G) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_Y \in E^{C'}(t)(F) \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_{X \cap Y} \in E^{C'}(t)(G \cup F)$
- 5.2.1. Consider any $t \in S$. Let $G, F \subseteq N$, be some groups of agents such that $G \cap F = \emptyset$. Assume $\widetilde{\phi}_X \in E^{C'}(t)(G)$ and $\widetilde{\phi}_Y \in E^{C'}(t)(F)$.
- 5.2.2. $\widetilde{\phi}_X \cap \widetilde{\phi}_Y \in E^{C'}(t)(G \cup F)$, from 5.2.1, because $E^{C'}(t)$ is superadditive.
- 5.2.3. $\widetilde{\phi}_{X \cap Y} \in E^{C'}(t)(G \cup F)$, from 5.2.2, because $\widetilde{\phi}_X \cap \widetilde{\phi}_Y = \widetilde{\phi}_{X \cap Y}$.
- 5.3. Case $G = N$ or $F = N$:
- 5.3.1. Note that the G or F that is not N , must be \emptyset . Thus, rename X & Y to X' & Y' , such that $X' \in E^f(s^f)(N)$ and $Y' \in E^f(s^f)(\emptyset)$.
- 5.3.2. $\exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f$ and $\widetilde{\phi}_{X'} \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, and $\forall u \in S^{C'}, s^f = u^f \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_{Y'} \in E^{C'}(u)(\emptyset)$ from 5.3.1 by definition of E^f .
- 5.3.3. $\exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f$ and $\widetilde{\phi}_{X' \cap Y'} \in E^{C'}(t)(N)$, from 5.2 & 5.3.2.
- 5.3.4. $X' \cap Y' \in E^f(s^f)(G' \cup F')$, from 5.3.2, by definition of E^f
- 5.4. Case $G \neq N$ and $F \neq N$
- 5.4.1. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_X \in E^{C'}(t)(G)$, and $\forall u \in S^{C'}, s^f = u^f \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_Y \in E^{C'}(u)(F)$, from 5.1, by definition of E^f .
- 5.4.2. Case $G \cup F = N$: $\exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f$ and $\widetilde{\phi}_{X \cap Y} \in E^{C'}(t)(G \cup F)$, when $t = s$ from 5.2 & 5.4.1. Thus, $X \cap Y \in E^f(s^f)(G \cup F)$, by definition of E^f .
- 5.4.3. Case $G \cup F \neq N$: $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow \widetilde{\phi}_{X \cap Y} \in E^{C'}(t)(G \cup F)$, from 5.2 & 5.4.1. Thus $X \cap Y \in E^f(s^f)(G \cup F)$, by definition of E^f .

We briefly elaborate here on step 3.5, as this step is non-trivial in Lean. Firstly, we note that in Lean we directly prove that $\widetilde{\phi}_{X^c} = \neg \widetilde{\phi}_X$, to make step 3.6 slightly simpler. We prove this by showing $\forall u, u \in \widetilde{\phi}_{X^c} \leftrightarrow u \in \neg \widetilde{\phi}_X$ (line 5). Because u is maximally consistent, this is the same as $\vdash \phi_{X^c} \leftrightarrow \neg \phi_X$. In the \Rightarrow direction, this is trivially equal to Lemma 4. The \Leftarrow direction, on the other hand, requires some further expansion to derive from Lemma 5. This work is performed by `phi_X_set_unique` (line 9), which is another Lean **lemma** that has a version for a Lean `list`, `finset` and `set`. We focus on the `list` version, which proves $\phi_X \leftrightarrow \neg \phi_Y$, so long as $X \cap Y = \emptyset$. The proof is inductive on X (or `sfs`, on line 23) and then Y (or `tfS`, on line 28). The cases when either X or Y are empty are trivial (lines 24 & 29-30). Given X contains at least one element s^f ($X = s^f \cup X'$), we can split $\vdash (\phi^{s^f} \vee \phi_{X'}) \rightarrow \neg \phi_Y$ into

two cases, the latter is solved with the induction hypothesis (lines 42-44). For the former, if Y contains at least one element t^f ($Y = t^f \cup Y'$), we can again split the contra-positive of our goal ($\vdash (\phi^{t^f} \vee \phi_{Y'}) \rightarrow \neg \phi^{sf}$) into two cases. Here, we can finally apply Lemma 5 to the former case $\vdash \phi^{t^f} \rightarrow \neg \phi^{sf}$ (lines 35-57). The latter is solved with the (new) induction hypothesis (lines 38-41).

```

1  have h_tilde: tilde (M.f.states) (phi_X_set Xc) =
2    tilde (M.f.states) (¬' (phi_X_set X)), from
3  begin
4    unfold tilde phi_X_set,
5    ext1 u,
6    split,
7    { intro hu,
8      apply max_ax_contains_by_set_proof u.2 hu
9        (phi_X_set_unique hcl (compl_inter_self X)), },
10   { intro hu,
11     apply max_ax_contains_by_set_proof u.2 hu,
12     apply (phi_X_set_disjunct_of_disjuncts _).mpr,
13     rw (union_compl_self X),
14     apply univ_disjunct_provability, },
15  end,
16
17  lemma phi_X_list_unique {agents form : Type} ...
18    {sfs tfs : list (S_f (canonical_model_CL _ _ hnpr) cl ψ)}
19    (hdis : sfs.disjoint tfs) :
20    ⊢' ((finite_disjunction (phi_X_list sfs)) →'
21      (¬' (finite_disjunction (phi_X_list tfs)))) :=
22  begin
23    induction' sfs with sf sfs ihsfs,
24    { simp only [phi_X_list, finite_disjunction, explosion], },
25    { simp only [phi_X_list, finite_disjunction],
26      apply or_cases,
27      -- ⊢ phi sf → ¬ phi tfs
28      { induction tfs with tf tfs ihtfs,
29        { unfold phi_X_list finite_disjunction,
30          exact mp _ _ (p1 _ _) iden, },
31        { simp only [phi_X_list, finite_disjunction, ...] at *,
32          -- ⊢ phi tfs → ¬ phi sf ⇒ ⊢ phi sf → ¬ phi tfs
33          apply contrapos.mp, apply cut (dne),
34          apply or_cases,
35          -- ⊢ phi tf → ¬ phi sf
36          { apply unique_s_f hcl, by_contradiction,
37            simp only [h, ...] at hdis, exact hdis, },
38          -- ⊢ phi tfs' → ¬ phi sf (proved with ihtfs)
39          { rw ←contrapos,
40            apply cut, apply dne, apply ihtfs,
41            exact hdis.2.1, exact hdis.2.2, }, }, },
42      -- ⊢ phi sfs' → ¬ phi tfs (proved with ihsfs)
43      { apply ihsfs hcl,

```

44 apply list.disjoint_of_disjoint_cons_left hdis, }, },
 45 **end**

Truth Lemma. Next we show that the filtered canonical model is set up so that the formulas contained in each state are also true in that state. For this section we will need to describe “common knowledge paths”, so for this we will use the notation $s^f \approx_G^f t^f := (s^f, t^f) \in (\bigcup_{i \in G} \sim_i^f)^*$. Let M^f be the model created when filtering $M^{C'}$ through $cl(\varphi)$.

Lemma 8 (CLC Truth Lemma [1, Theorem 1]). *Truth Lemma : a formula is true in a world in S^f iff it is contained by that world. $\forall s \in S^{C'}, \forall \psi \in cl(\varphi), M^f, s^f \models \psi$ iff $\psi \in s^f$.*

This proof is by induction on ψ . The cases for atomic propositions and propositional operators are straightforward from the fact that s^f is consistent. We focus on the cases $[G]\psi$, $K_i\psi$ and $C_G\psi$.

Case $[G]\psi$, where $G = N$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & M^f, s^f \models [N]\psi \\
 \Leftrightarrow & \{s^f \in S^f \mid M^f, s^f \models \psi\} \in E^f(s^f)(N), \text{ by definition of } \models \\
 \Leftrightarrow & \exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \text{ and } \tilde{\phi}_{\{s^f \in S^f \mid M^f, s^f \models \psi\}} \in E^{C'}(t)(N), \text{ by definition of } \\
 & E^f. \\
 \Leftrightarrow & \exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \text{ and } \tilde{\phi}_{\{s^f \in S^f \mid \psi \in s^f\}} \in E^{C'}(t)(N), \text{ by the inductive} \\
 & \text{hypothesis } (\forall s \in S^{C'}, M^f, s^f \models \psi \text{ iff } \psi \in s^f). \\
 \Leftrightarrow & \exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \text{ and } \tilde{\psi} \in E^{C'}(t)(N), \text{ by Lemma 6.} \\
 \Leftrightarrow & \exists t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \text{ and } [N]\psi \in t, \text{ by Lemma 7.} \\
 \Leftrightarrow & [N]\psi \in s^f, \text{ from left to right because if we fix such a } t, \text{ then } [N]\psi \in t^f \\
 & \text{and } s^f = t^f, \text{ and from right to left when } s = t.
 \end{aligned}$$

Case $[G]\psi$, where $G \neq N$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & M^f, s^f \models [G]\psi \\
 \Leftrightarrow & \{s^f \in S^f \mid M^f, s^f \models \psi\} \in E^f(s^f)(G), \text{ by definition of } \models \\
 \Leftrightarrow & \forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \text{ and } \tilde{\phi}_{\{s^f \in S^f \mid M^f, s^f \models \psi\}} \in E^{C'}(t)(G), \text{ by definition of } E^f. \\
 \Leftrightarrow & \forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow \tilde{\phi}_{\{s^f \in S^f \mid \psi \in s^f\}} \in E^{C'}(t)(G), \text{ by the inductive} \\
 & \text{hypothesis } (\forall s \in S^{C'}, M^f, s^f \models \psi \text{ iff } \psi \in s^f). \\
 \Leftrightarrow & \forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow \tilde{\psi} \in E^{C'}(t)(G), \text{ by Lemma 6.} \\
 \Leftrightarrow & \forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f = t^f \Rightarrow [G]\psi \in t, \text{ by Lemma 7.} \\
 \Leftrightarrow & [G]\psi \in s^f, \text{ from left to right when } s = t, \text{ and from right to left because} \\
 & [G]\psi \in s^f \text{ and so for any } t \text{ such that } t^f = s^f, [G]\psi \in t^f.
 \end{aligned}$$

Case $K_i\psi \Rightarrow$:

1. Let $M^f, s^f \models K_i\psi$.
2. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f \sim_i^f t^f \Rightarrow M^f, t^f \models \psi$, from 1, by definition of \models .
3. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f \sim_i^f t^f \Rightarrow \psi \in t^f$, from 2, by the induction hypothesis ($\forall s \in S^{C'}, M^f, s^f \models \psi \Leftrightarrow \psi \in s^f$).
4. Assume towards a contradiction that $K_i\psi \notin s^f$.
5. $\neg K_i\psi \in s$, from 4, because s is maximally consistent.

6. Consider the set $\Sigma = \{\chi \mid K_i\chi \in s\}$.
 7. $\Sigma \cup \{\neg\psi\}$ is consistent.
 - 7.1. Assume towards a contradiction $\Sigma \cup \{\neg\psi\}$ is inconsistent.
 - 7.2. Consider some $\Sigma' \subseteq \Sigma$ such that Σ' is finite and $\vdash (\bigwedge_{\chi \in \Sigma'} \chi) \rightarrow \psi$, which exists by 7.1, by propositional logic.
 - 7.3. $\vdash K_i((\bigwedge_{\chi \in \Sigma'} \chi) \rightarrow \psi)$, from 7.2, by axiom **(RN)**.
 - 7.4. $\vdash (K_i(\bigwedge_{\chi \in \Sigma'} \chi)) \rightarrow K_i\psi$, from 7.3, by axiom **(K)**.
 - 7.5. $\vdash (\bigwedge_{\chi \in \Sigma'} K_i\chi) \rightarrow K_i\psi$, from 7.4, by propositional logic and axiom **(RN)**.
 - 7.6. $(\bigwedge_{\chi \in \Sigma'} K_i\chi) \in s$, by definition of Σ , from 6.
 - 7.7. $K_i\psi \in s$, from 7.5 & 7.6.
 - 7.8. Contradiction from 5 and 7.7.
 8. Consider some $t \in S^{C'}$ such that $\Sigma \cup \{\neg\psi\} \subseteq t$, which exists by 7, by definition of $S^{C'}$. Note that $\neg\psi \in t$.
 9. $s^f \sim_i^f t^f$.
 - 9.1. $\forall \chi, K_i\chi \in s^f \rightarrow K_i\chi \in t^f$. Assume $K_i\chi \in s^f$, then $K_i\chi \in cl(\varphi)$ and $K_i(K_i\chi) \in s$, by axiom **(4)**. So $K_i\chi \in \Sigma$, by definition Σ and $K_i\chi \in t$, by 8.
 - 9.2. $\forall \chi, K_i\chi \in t^f \rightarrow K_i\chi \in s^f$. Assume $K_i\chi \in t^f$. Assume towards a contradiction $K_i\chi \notin s^f$. Then $K_i(\neg K_i\chi) \in s$, by axiom **(5)**. So $\neg K_i\chi \in \Sigma$, by definition Σ and $\neg K_i\chi \in t$, by 8. This means t is not consistent which is a contradiction.
 10. $\psi \in t$, from 3 and 9
 11. Contradiction from 8 & 10.
- Case $K_i\psi \Leftarrow$:
1. Let $K_i\psi \in s^f$.
 2. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f \sim_i^f t^f \Rightarrow K_i\psi \in t^f$, from 1, by definition of \sim_i^f .
 3. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f \sim_i^f t^f \Rightarrow \psi \in t^f$, from 2, by axiom **(T)**.
 4. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f \sim_i^f t^f \Rightarrow M^f, t^f \models \psi$, from 3, by the induction hypothesis ($\forall s \in S^{C'}, M^f, s^f \models \psi \Leftrightarrow \psi \in s^f$).
 5. $M^f, s^f \models K_i\psi$, by the definition of \models , from 4.
- Case $C_G\psi \Rightarrow$:
1. Let $M^f, s^f \models C_G\psi$.
 2. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f \approx_G^f t^f \rightarrow M^f, t^f \models \psi$, from 1, by definition of \approx .
 3. $\forall t \in S^{C'}, s^f \approx_G^f t^f \rightarrow \psi \in t^f$, from 2, by the induction hypothesis ($\forall s \in S^{C'}, M^f, s^f \models \psi \Leftrightarrow \psi \in s^f$).
 4. Let $\Gamma = \{u \in S^{C'} \mid \forall v \in S^{C'}, u^f \approx_G^f v^f \rightarrow \psi \in v^f\}$.
Let Γ^f be the corresponding filtered set $\{u^f : u \in \Gamma\}$.
 5. $s \in \Gamma$, from 3, by definition of Γ (from 4).
 6. $\vdash \phi^{s^f} \rightarrow \phi_{\Gamma^f}$, from 5, by propositional logic.
 7. $G \neq \emptyset \Rightarrow \forall u \in \Gamma, \psi \in u^f$, by definition of Γ , from 4.
 8. $G \neq \emptyset \Rightarrow \vdash \phi_{\Gamma^f} \rightarrow \psi$, from 7, by propositional logic.
 9. $\vdash \phi_{\Gamma^f} \rightarrow E_G\phi_{\Gamma^f}$.
 - 9.1. Assume towards a contradiction that $\neg(\phi_{\Gamma^f} \rightarrow E_G\phi_{\Gamma^f})$ is consistent.
 - 9.2. Consider some $w \in S^{C'}$, such that $\neg(\phi_{\Gamma^f} \rightarrow E_G\phi_{\Gamma^f}) \in w$, which exists by 9.1.

- 9.3. $\phi_{\Gamma^f} \wedge \neg E_G \phi_{\Gamma^f} \in w$, from 9.2, by propositional logic.
- 9.4. Consider some $x \in \Gamma$ such that $\phi^{x^f} \in w$, which exists by 9.3.
- 9.5. Consider some $i \in G$ such that $\neg K_i \phi_{\Gamma^f} \in w$, which exists by 9.3.
- 9.6. $\neg K_i \neg \phi_{(\Gamma^f)^c} \in w$, from 9.5, by propositional logic, axiom **(K)** and Lemma 4.
- 9.7. Consider some $y \in \Gamma^c$ such that $\neg K_i \neg \phi^{y^f} \in w$, which exists by 9.6, using propositional logic and axiom **(K)**.
- 9.8. Consider some $z \in S^{C'}$ such that $y^f \approx_G^f z^f$ and $\psi \notin z^f$ which exists by 9.7 given the definition of Γ and thus Γ^c .
- 9.9. We show $x^f \sim_i^f y^f$.
- 9.9.1. $\forall \chi, K_i \chi \in x^f \rightarrow K_i \chi \in y^f$.
 Consider some χ , such that $K_i \chi \in x^f$. Assume towards a contradiction that $K_i \chi \notin y^f$. Then, $\vdash K_i \chi \rightarrow \neg \phi^{y^f}$. $\vdash \neg K_i \neg \phi^{y^f} \rightarrow \neg K_i K_i \chi$, by propositional logic and axiom **(K)**. $\neg K_i K_i \chi \in w$, from this and 9.7. However, also $K_i K_i \chi \in w$, from 9.4, because $K_i \chi \in x^f$ and by Axiom **(4)**. Contradiction.
- 9.9.2. $\forall \chi, K_i \chi \in y^f \rightarrow K_i \chi \in x^f$.
 Consider some χ , such that $K_i \chi \in y^f$. Assume towards a contradiction that $K_i \chi \notin x^f$. We have $\vdash \neg K_i \chi \rightarrow \neg \phi^{y^f}$. $\vdash \neg K_i \neg \phi^{y^f} \rightarrow \neg K_i \neg K_i \chi$, by propositional logic and axiom **(K)**. $\neg K_i \neg K_i \chi \in w$, from this and 9.7. $K_i \chi \in w$, by propositional logic and axiom **(5)**. However, also $\neg K_i \chi \in w$, from 9.4, because $K_i \chi \notin x^f$. Contradiction.
- 9.10. $\psi \in z^f$, because $x \in \Gamma$ (from 9.4) and there is a path $x^f \sim_i^f y^f$ (from 9.9), $y^f \approx_G^f z^f$ (from 9.8).
- 9.11. Contradiction from 9.8 & 9.10.
10. $\vdash \phi_{\Gamma} \rightarrow C_G \psi$, from 8 & 9, by axiom **(RC)**.
11. $C_G \psi \in s^f$, from 6 & 10, by propositional logic.
- Case $C_G \psi \Leftarrow$:
1. Assume $C_G \psi \in s^f$, and let t^f be some world such that $s^f \approx_G^f t^f$. Thus, we need to show $M^f, t^f \models \psi$.
 2. Let us show $\forall u, v \in S^{C'}, \forall i \in G, C_G \psi \in u^f \rightarrow (u^f \sim_i^f v^f \rightarrow (\psi \in v^f \wedge C_G \psi \in v^f))$
 - 2.1. Let $u, v \in S^{C'}$ be some worlds, and let $i \in G$ be some agent such that $C_G \psi \in u^f$ and $u^f \sim_i^f v^f$.
 - 2.2. $K_i(C_G \psi) \in u^f$, from 2.1 ($C_G \psi \in u^f$), by definition of $cl(C_G \psi)$, propositional logic, and axioms **(C)**, **(K)** and **(RN)**.
 - 2.3. $K_i(C_G \psi) \in v^f$ from 2.1 ($u^f \sim_i^f v^f$) & 2.2, by definition of \sim_i^f .
 - 2.4. $C_G \psi \in v^f$, from 2.3, by axiom **(T)**.
 - 2.5. $\psi \in v^f$, from 2.4, by propositional logic, and axioms **(T)**, **(C)**, **(K)** and **(RN)**.
 3. Let us describe the "path" $s^f \approx_G^f t^f$ as $\langle s^f, \sim_{i_0}^f, s_1^f, \sim_{i_1}^f, s_2^f, \dots, s_n^f, \sim_n^f, t^f \rangle$, such that $s^f \sim_{i_0}^f s_1^f, s_1^f \sim_{i_1}^f s_2^f, \dots, s_n^f \sim_{i_n}^f t^f$ and $\{i_0, i_1, \dots, i_n\} \subseteq G$. This path has length n , where n is equal to the number of states in the path between s^f and t^f . We prove $M^f, t^f \models \psi$, by induction on the length n , of this path.

- 3.1. Base case ($n = 0$). Our path is $\langle s^f, \sim_{i_0}^f, t^f \rangle$, where $s^f \sim_{i_0}^f t^f$. Note that, due to our assumptions in 1 we do not consider the base case of the path to be the single point s^f . If we did consider the base case of the path to be the single point $\langle s^f \rangle$, we must still have $s^f \sim_{i_0}^f s^f$, for some $i_0 \in G$, because any $i \in G$ must have a reflexive epistemic relation in s^f , and G cannot be empty from 1. Thus the following reasoning would still hold for the base case $\langle s^f \rangle$.
- 3.1.1. $\psi \in t^f$, from 2, because $C_G \psi \in s^f$ (from 1), and $s^f \sim_{i_0}^f t^f$ (from 3.1).
- 3.1.2. $M^f, t^f \models \psi$, from 3.1.1, by the induction hypothesis for the truth lemma ($\forall s \in S^{C'}, M^f, s^f \models \psi \leftrightarrow \psi \in s^f$).
- 3.2. Inductive step ($n + 1$). Our path is $\langle s^f, \sim_i^f, u^f, \sim_{i_0}^f, s_1^f, \dots, s_n^f, \sim_n^f, t^f \rangle$. Note here that if this path has length $n + 1$, the path of length n would be the path $\langle u^f, \sim_{i_0}^f, s_1^f, \dots, s_n^f, \sim_n^f, t^f \rangle$. Thus we are increasing the length of the path by adding to the front, rather than the back. This choice is made to match the Lean implementation of such a path.
- Induction hypothesis for the path : for all $u \in S^{C'}$ such that $C_G \psi \in u^f$, if u^f and t^f are connected by the path $\langle u^f, \sim_{i_0}^f, s_1^f, \dots, s_n^f, \sim_n^f, t^f \rangle$ (of length n), then $M^f, t^f \models \psi$.
- 3.2.1. $C_G \psi \in u^f$, from 2, because $C_G \psi \in s^f$ (from 1), and $s^f \sim_i^f u^f$ (from 3.2).
- 3.2.2. $M^f, t^f \models \psi$, from 3.2 by the Induction Hypothesis for the path, because $C_G \psi \in u^f$ (from 3.2.1) and $u^f \approx_G^f t^f$, by the path $\langle u^f, \sim_{i_0}^f, s_1^f, \dots, s_n^f, \sim_n^f, t^f \rangle$ (from 3.2).

In Lean we prove the corresponding **lemma** `truth_lemma_CLC` :

```

1 lemma truth_lemma_CLC {agents : Type} [ha : nonempty agents]
2   [hN : fintype agents] (ψ ψ : formCLC agents)
3   (sf : (Mf_CLC ψ).f.states) (hψ : ψ ∈ cl ψ) :
4   ((Mf_CLC ψ); sf '⊨ ψ) ↔ (ψ ∈ sf) := ...

```

The full Lean proof is omitted here due to similarity with the above paper proof, but can be found in file `completeness/completenessCLC.lean`.

Completeness.

Theorem 4 (Completeness of CLC [1, Corollary 1]). $\forall \varphi, \models \varphi \Rightarrow \vdash \varphi$

Proof. We prove this Lemma similarly to CL: every CLC consistent formula φ exists in some state M^f , where M^f has been created by filtering $M^{C'}$ through $cl(\varphi)$. By Lemma 8, φ is also true in that state.

The Lean proof for completeness can be found in the file `completeness/completenessCLC.lean`.

```

1 theorem completenessCLC {agents : Type}
2   [ha : nonempty agents] [hN : fintype agents]
3   (ψ : formCLC agents) : ('⊢ ψ) → '⊢ ψ :=

```

We have, thus, verified our defined syntax and semantics of CLC in Lean by proving both soundness and completeness. Finally, we do the same for Coalition Logic with individual knowledge, by the same proof as above, removing any parts related to common knowledge. In Lean, we can do this by adjusting the files that define the syntax and semantics of the logic (`syntax/syntaxCLK.lean` & `semantics/semanticsCLK.lean`), the file with closure definitions and lemmas (`completeness/closureCLK.lean`), and the files with inductive proofs (`soundness/soundnessCLK.lean` & `completeness/completenessCLK.lean`). All Lean lemmas and definitions about model construction can be reused to prove that CLK is sound and complete. The same can also be done in the case that we want to require a coalition model to be truly playable. This change would naturally require us to redefine our semantics in Lean, as it was specific to the playable coalition model. We provide an example of this in the file `completeness/completenessCLtrueplay.lean`, along with the proofs of soundness and completeness.

4 Conclusion

In this work we have described the successful implementation of soundness and completeness proofs for CL and CLC in Lean, answering **RQ1**, and **RQ2**: *How do soundness and completeness proofs of CL / CLC work in Lean?* For CL this implementation was quite straightforward. Many of the specific implementation choices in this work were decided based on previous work [26]. The main challenge was thus, elaborating on consistency and S^C : the set of all maximally consistent sets. Although we did not have to prove Lindenbaum’s lemma from scratch, we did have to go into detail in Lean about the relevant properties of maximally consistent sets. A good example of this is the extra steps required to prove that if no maximally consistent set contains φ , then $\vdash \varphi \leftrightarrow \perp$ as described when proving playability of the canonical model in Section 2.

For CLC the implementation was a little more complex, as dealing with finiteness in Lean adds considerable complexity, compared to a paper proof. Initially this complexity is due to the fact that data structures in Lean are defined strictly, and so we needed to switch between them at different points. More specifically, in Lean lists are finite and ordered, but sets are unordered and may be infinite. In order to iterate over each element in a set, in Lean we thus first needed to translate that `set` into a `finset` (finite set) and then into a `list`. Only then can formulas like $E_G\varphi$ or ϕ^{s^f} be defined in Lean. In and of itself these translations can feel bulky and unintuitive, however, they are fairly simple to implement. When proving lemmas about these formulas, however, we often needed to prove the lemmas given the `list`. Only then could we perform induction, to consider separate elements of a conjunction or

disjunction. Separate lemmas were then needed to indicate that the same lemma would hold for a `finset`, given that it could be translated into a `list`, and a `set`, given that it could be translated into a `finset`. Any relevant properties of the set, for instance that there were no repeating elements, would therefore have to be manually passed forward, through each of these different lemmas. These translations, therefore added a lot of work, although again most of it was trivial.

In addition to needing to deal with finiteness, there were many trivial properties about the finite closure (cl) and filtered model (M^f), that needed to be made explicit in Lean, similarly to how we had to elaborate on the properties of consistency for CL. For instance, proving that cl is closed under single negations is a long proof in Lean, given how many cases need to be considered, despite being trivial. Aside from these factors however, the completeness proof did translate pretty directly to Lean.

As for modularity, we implemented generic Lean `classes` for each logic’s syntax and axiomatic system in order to answer **RQ3**: *How can definitions of and theorems about CL in Lean be reused for CLC?* These `classes` allowed us to use the same lemmas, regardless of which logic we were using. Additionally, we were able to fully reuse our defined canonical model M^c from our CL completeness proof, to prove completeness for CLC, with essentially as much ease as in the paper proof. Similarly, we were able to reuse our definition for the filtered model, for both CLC and CLK.

Finally, we also demonstrated that researchers can successfully elaborate on each others work on completeness proofs in Lean. As already mentioned the current work relied heavily on the thesis by Neely [26]. Although we could not directly use their Lean code as it was specific to their syntax and semantics, we were easily able to adjust a lot of Neely’s code to work for our defined syntax and semantics, or for our generic classes. This again, reinforces the idea that Lean completeness proofs, even those with deep embeddings, can build upon each other in similar ways that paper proofs can.

5 Applications

As we have already mentioned, modal logic is a natural and useful way to describe the functioning of applications in MAS, and to check whether their designs meet requirements [15,18,21,37]. We chose to focus on CLC due to the fact that many modern problems involve multiple agents and imperfect knowledge [15,34]. Now we look a little closer at how the syntax and semantics of CLC defined in Lean by this work might be applied to solve problems in MAS. We examine one potential algorithm that could be used to check design requirements: model checking, however we leave implementation in Lean for future research.

5.1 Model Checking

Requirements in modal logic will most likely be given as a formula that either needs to be true in a specific state or needs to be true somewhere in the model.

In our lightbulb example (Figure 2) for instance, we might want to know whether the controller and receiver can ever ensure the light is on $[\{c, r\}]l$. Note that here we are interested in working with (checking specifications in) an already defined model. This contrasts our completeness proofs where we were building a model that meets some specification.

Algorithms that check the truth of some formula in a model are known as model checking algorithms. Specifically, these are algorithms that for some φ , and some model $M := (S, E, \{\sim_i: i \in N\}, V)$, return the set of states in the model where φ is true: $\{s \mid M, s \models \varphi\}$. Such an algorithm can be defined recursively on φ . For readability we let $\tilde{\varphi} := \{s \mid M, s \models \varphi\}$. For the propositional, effectivity and individual knowledge operators, as well as common knowledge of the empty group, such an algorithm is simple :

$$\begin{aligned} \perp &:= \emptyset \\ \tilde{p} &:= \{s \mid M, s \models p\} \\ \widetilde{\varphi \wedge \psi} &:= \tilde{\varphi} \cap \tilde{\psi} \\ \widetilde{\varphi \rightarrow \psi} &:= (\tilde{\varphi})^c \cup \tilde{\psi} \\ \widetilde{[G]\varphi} &:= \{s \mid \tilde{\varphi} \in E(s)(G)\} \\ \widetilde{K_i\varphi} &:= \{s \mid \forall t, s \sim_i t \rightarrow t \in \tilde{\varphi}\} \\ \widetilde{C_\emptyset\varphi} &:= S \end{aligned}$$

The case for common knowledge of a nonempty group is a little more complex, as we need to consider the “path” of common knowledge. We, thus, build the set $\widetilde{C_G\varphi}$, when $G \neq \emptyset$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma^0 &:= \tilde{\varphi} \\ \Gamma^{n+1} &:= \{s \in \Gamma^n \mid \forall t, \forall i \in G, s \sim_i t \rightarrow t \in \Gamma^n\} \end{aligned}$$

The algorithm stops when $\Gamma^{n+1} = \Gamma^n$, in which case $\widetilde{C_G\varphi} = \Gamma^n$. The algorithm works, because if $M, s \models C_G\varphi$ and $s \approx_G t$, then $M, t \models C_G\varphi$, due to the knowledge relations being equivalence relations. We begin with Γ^0 , with all the states where φ is true. Then, to build Γ^1 , for each of those states s , the algorithm looks at the states t that are indistinguishable from s by some agent $i \in G$, so states where $s \sim_i t$. We only keep s if all those states t also contain φ . Γ^1 now contains the states where $C_G\varphi$ would be true if “common knowledge paths” had a maximum of “length” of one individual knowledge relation. Each following set Γ^n essentially contains the states where $C_G\varphi$ would be true if common “knowledge paths” had a maximum of “length” of n individual knowledge relations. Note that the set either shrinks every iteration, or the algorithm ends. Given a finite starting set the algorithm must, therefore, terminate.

6 Discussion

Translating the completeness proofs for CL and CLC into Lean highlights the challenges that make this kind of formalization relatively uncommon [13]. The need to explicitly define every trivial definition or lemma can make formalization time-consuming and tedious. In the current work this was especially apparent when needing to translate between different data structures. We note, however,

that some of these difficulties may also be coming from trying to stick reasonably close to the paper proofs. For instance, defining conjunctions and disjunctions with first-order \forall and \exists statements, may have been more natural in Lean. The latter allows us to break conjunctions and disjunctions into the elements without needing to change between data structures. In fact, and for this reason, we often converted into first order logical formulas in Lean for our proofs.

Another potential solution to the tedious nature of formalization is increased automation. Especially very simple but long proofs, like showing that $cl(\varphi)$ is closed under single negations, we think are ideal candidates for better proof automation in Lean. We thus believe that this may be an interesting topic for future research.

Being explicit, however, also comes with advantages, on top of being computer-readable. Doing so allows us to be precise about exactly when we use hypotheses and assumptions. Most notably, this led to us easily showing that the completeness proof for CLC described by Ågotnes and Alechina [1] also holds if we change the syntax to allow the formula $C_\emptyset\varphi$. Programmatic formalization lends itself well to these tests of generalization; it automates the work of re-checking an entire proof every time a hypothesis is slightly changed or removed [4,13].

Another potential advantage of formalization that may at first seem counter intuitive, is that it may be more accessible. While mathematicians may find it tedious to be explicit about every assumption and step in a proof, for individuals outside of this background it may provide clarity. Not every individual will have the same idea of which steps are “trivial”, or what exact properties can be assumed from existing theories. Using a proof assistant means we explicitly know when something does and does not need elaboration. Considering that MAS is a field of AI, not mathematics, this extra clarity may be vital. Applications in MAS may stray into fields like Human Computer Interaction in our light-bulb example, or Information Technology in our device management example, where we may encounter individuals without a rigorous mathematical background in proof construction.

Even for those with a mathematical background, the concept of a mathematical proof can be vague [16]. For this reason proof assistants are beginning to be used as a teaching tool in mathematics and computer science [12,32,35]. Preliminary qualitative studies indicate that using proof assistants in this way leads to students being more accurate and clear in their paper proofs, and more consistently breaking their goals into clear sub-goals [32,35]. Whether these tools do in fact help teams working on MAS applications of modal logic would be an interesting direction for future research.

Research more closely related to our work may look to expand on our efforts to make the completeness proofs modular and reusable. Although we made generic `classes` for each logic’s syntax and axiomatic systems, we did not do the same for the logic’s semantics. This choice was made, as the semantics are only used in inductive proofs. We could not use our generic `classes` for inductive proofs, as they essentially acted as minimum requirements for the syntax and proof system of some logic, and thus did not store every case as would

be needed to perform induction. However, each individual case in an inductive proof could be separated into its own lemma if semantics were added to the generic `classes`. Future work could, thus, look into expanding our `classes` and creating such generic proofs. Even more interesting would be to define the logics in such a way that we can use generic data structures for inductive proofs.

Finally, CLC is not the only type of Epistemic Coalition Logic described by Ågotnes and Alechina [1]. A natural area for future research would thus be to formalize the other types as well.

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